

PROMISING CASES ON
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INTRODUCTION

Each year, a considerable number of third-country nationals (TCNs) are required to leave the European Union, including individuals whose asylum claims have been rejected, irregular migrants apprehended within EU territory, and those whose residence permits have expired or been withdrawn. However, there are various limits to the implementation of ‘voluntary’ or forced return including constraints under international and human rights law, difficult cooperation with countries of origin, bureaucratic obstacles such as the lack of identification documents or protests in local communities (Ambrosini, 2016; Castañeda, 2010; Leerkes & Van Houte, 2020). Across Europe, a persistent gap exists between the number of TCNs who receive an order to leave (‘return decision’) and those who demonstrably leave the territory, leaving many irregularly staying migrants in precarious situations with often little access to basic rights and services. Given that these limits to return are unlikely to be fully overcome in the future - as states will have to continue to rely on third-country cooperation, respect international and human rights law, and consider societal costs of deportation - it becomes increasingly relevant to find adequate responses to protracted situations of non-return and persistent irregularity.

States across Europe have adopted different policies to deal with protracted situations of non-return, ranging from regularization programs and mechanisms to toleration statuses, institutional abandonment or recurring detention (Ince Beqo et al., 2025). Arguably, existing non-return policies differ along at least three dimensions: their rights allocation (ranging from more restrictive to liberal), their reach (number of persons targeted and obtaining access in practice), and the degree to which they are explicit or implicit in their legal and political acknowledgment of the difficulties that states experience in enforcing return of the groups being targeted. These differences manifest both in the conditions individuals must meet to access such policies and in the rights they are granted under them. Importantly, non-return policies do not evolve in a social or political vacuum. They are embedded in particular policy contexts and inextricably linked to other dimensions of national migration governance.

This working paper discusses promising non-return policies that have emerged across Europe to manage the continued presence of TCNs who do not or cannot (be) return(ed). We assess the benefits and costs of selected non-return policies from a multi-actor perspective, paying particular attention to individual’s capabilities, societal dimensions (including economic, political and legal perspectives) and human rights performance. We focus on groups of irregular migrants who are in contact with the immigration authorities and therefore have received, or could receive, a return decision under European law. We conceive of *promising* non-return policies as policies that are (1) respectful to human rights and capable of promoting human development, (2) potentially beneficial for host societies, and (3) politically feasible within their respective country context. Ideally, promising non-return policies could also be ‘transferred’ to other policy contexts, or could at least broaden horizons in different European contexts by providing more information about viable solutions for non-return that have emerged elsewhere in Europe. More specifically, the working paper focuses on potentially promising non-return policies in five EU+ countries which have implemented different non-return policies that seem to provide promising solutions: Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, Poland, and Switzerland—each representing a distinct post-arrival enforcement regime.

The empirical case studies revolve around the following research questions:

- (1) Which promising non-return policies exist in the selected countries and what are their objectives?

- (2) What can be said about the reach of these non-return policies?
- (3) How do existing alternatives align with human rights and promote migrants' capabilities?
- (4) What can be said about their societal costs and benefits (economic, political, legal)?

By examining these cases, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how states have responded to the practical and normative challenges of non-return and persistent irregularity. We know that countries have, to some extent, different post-arrival enforcement regimes, with some countries - and some locations within these countries - being more interested in, and/or capable of, enforcing migration return (cf. Leerkes and Van Houte, 2020). Additionally, there is an increased political interest to enforce migrant return, both in Europe and elsewhere, which takes these regimes in more enforcement-oriented directions. The analysis helps us understand how non-return policies are a by-product, or even an integral element, of different regimes – *including* the more enforcement-oriented regimes – and what could be the implications if the strong interest in enforcement persists.

THEORY

A conceptualization of promising non-return policies

Non-return accommodation policies - hereafter also: non-return policies - represent measures that states design or implicitly use to manage the continued presence of irregular migrants who have received or could have received a return decision under the European Return Directive, but whose return is difficult or impossible to enforce. In the analysis, we do not use the term 'alternatives to return', which circulates in the field of migration policymaking. In many cases, states still expect migrants that are targeted by non-return policies to return to their country of citizenship at some point, making the term 'alternatives to return' euphemistic and overly inclusionary. Non-return policies refer to all policies that seek to address proven or anticipated prolonged difficulties in enforcing return, which can result in regularization but also in protracted, 'controlled' irregular stay or in states allocating highly insecure 'liminal' (cf. Menjívar, 2006) legal statuses that are easily lost. In the analysis, we assume that different regularization policies can, at least in part, be seen as non-return accommodation policies, because difficulties in enforcing return are among the reasons why states provide such regularization opportunities. This is not to say that regularization policies are non-return accommodation policies per se: Italy, for example, has repeatedly regularized irregular workers "post hoc" in the past simply because the country lacked proper migrant admission policies (cf. Kraler, 2019). In the 1970s, the Dutch authorities frequently regularized irregular migrants – who were often called "spontaneous migrants" at the time – because they were seen as highly desirable, motivated workers (cf. Engbersen and Van der Leun, 2001).

Underlying dimensions

Amnesties and other regularization mechanisms are relatively inclusionary non-return policies, as they grant more rights to irregular migrants, even if those benefiting from them may still be at risk of falling back into irregularity, such as when migrants lose their employment in case of employment-related regularization (cf. Chauvin, Garcés-Mascreñas and Kraler, 2013). Other non-return policies are considerably more exclusionary: they take the form of (night) shelter, long term encampment or prolonged immigration detention without a real view to deportation and without opportunities to obtain long-term legal stay in the European country, leaving migrants stranded in insecure and precarious limbo situations (cf. Leerkes and Broeders, 2010; Johanssen, 2013, Vanderbruggen et al., 2014; Leerkes, 2016).

In the present study, we seek to analyze non-return policies that potentially provide promising solutions to protracted situations of non-return. As a result, we focus on relatively inclusionary non-return policies – regularization policies, hardship regulations or permits for humanitarian stay – that do not risk violating migrants’ fundamental rights. However, we also realized that there could be certain trade-offs between “rights” and “numbers” (cf. Ruhs, 2013): policies that are inclusionary in terms of rights allocated may be quite exclusionary in terms of the number of persons benefiting from them. We therefore assess non-return policies separately on their “rights” and “reach” dimension. Additionally, we did not want to limit ourselves to policies that states explicitly use to accommodate non-return (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024). If there is a strong interest in enforcing migrant return, states may be somewhat reluctant to acknowledge that they are using non-return policies (see for example Johansen, 2013 on the Norwegian “return centers” that accommodate prolonged irregular stay yet are sold politically as an instrument to still promote return). Such implicit non-return policies can be problematic in terms of migrants’ fundamental rights and rule of law; yet we did not want to exclude the possibility that implicit policies can still be promising, especially given the need for these policies to also be politically feasible, including in enforcement-oriented contexts. To capture policy variation across countries and contexts, we thus identify three analytical dimensions:

1. **Rights Allocation:** This dimension refers to the type and scope of rights granted to individuals who are targeted by a non-return policy. The examples assessed in the present paper which are located on the more inclusionary, rights-oriented end of the spectrum are policies such as Germany’s *Ausbildungsduldung*, Italy’s regularization program or Switzerland’s *Härtefallregelung* which grant access to employment and education, allowing migrants to eventually obtain a residence permit on the basis of their labour market qualifications or integration achievements, and ultimately provide a pathway to full citizenship. In Poland, we focused on permissions for humanitarian stay, that grant access to the labour market, as well as temporary residence permits that can be applied for by irregular migrants, aimed at protecting family life and the rights of the child. For the Netherlands, we focus on the *Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening (LVV) program*, which arguably scores the lowest on the ‘rights dimension’, at least for most migrants being targeted. The program funded temporary shelter for irregular migrants in combination with return and regularization counselling: for most migrants it only resulted in temporary shelter and limited regularization support while returns were still occurring to some extent (De La Maza Dias & Leerkes, 2024). It should be pointed out that policies that score the lowest on the ‘rights dimension’ have been excluded from the present analysis (e.g., prolonged detention, the encampment-style “return centers” in Scandinavia, and institutional abandonment of irregular migrants across Europe).
2. **Reach:** This dimension refers to the number of people potentially being targeted by, a non-return policy, and having actual access to it, reflecting their selectivity and accessibility. Some policies are narrowly targeted and discretionary, benefiting only a small number of individuals—such as Poland’s humanitarian and toleration statuses. Other policies are broader in scope, such as the large-scale regularization programs in Southern Europe or generalized non-enforcement strategies that apply to wide categories of migrants. Importantly, reach does not only depend on formal accessibility criteria; it also depends on the extent to which states actually use certain policies, and on the access that different groups have to rights that exist “in the books”. Access to such rights depends on migrants’ resources (cf. Lockwood, 1996), including their social, cultural, and symbolic capital (cf. Jonitz and Leerkes, 2022).

3. **Explicit vs. implicit framing.** This dimension refers to the extent to which policies formally and politically acknowledge the issue of non-return. As was mentioned in the above, some non-return policies are formally acknowledged and explicitly framed as such within official discourse and legal frameworks. These include the *Duldung* status – temporary suspension of deportation – and labor-related regularization mechanisms in Germany, Italy’s regularization programs, and Polish ‘conventions-related’ permits aimed at regularizing the stay of migrants to protect their family life or children’s rights. These policies are explicitly designed to address the situation of ‘non-removable’ migrants. Conversely, implicit non-return policies are not formally labeled as such but may functionally serve the same purpose. Policies of institutional abandonment – the non-enforcement of return decisions, often accompanied by a tolerance of irregular employment – are an example in point. Finally, semi-explicit non-return policies may be officially framed or presented as serving one goal (enforcing return), while implicitly serving another purpose at the same time (accommodating non-return). An example is the LVV program in the Netherlands, which was officially presented as a temporary return facilitation measure, while most migrants remained in the Netherlands.

Importantly, these dimensions do not necessarily align in a linear fashion. A policy can be liberal in terms of rights but restrictive in reach, or vice versa. For example, the *Härtefallregelung* grants significant rights but applies to relatively few people, whereas abandonment policies affect a large population but offer limited rights and protection. Implicit non-return policies can provide ample rights and have a considerable reach. Arguably, a case in point are the opportunities for partner-based regularization, where irregular migrants eventually obtain a family reunification residence permit via a host country spouse.

Non-return policies as element of post-arrival enforcement regimes

Non-return policies typically emerge at the intersection of migration enforcement, humanitarian concern, and political pragmatism. In many cases, these policies represent states’ attempts to manage the contradictions inherent in liberal democracies that simultaneously seek to uphold human rights, enforce immigration controls, protect national sovereignty, and ensure – in some countries more than in other countries – a sufficient supply of migrant labor (cf. Boswell, 2007). As such, non-return policies can be considered part of a broader political logic that acknowledges the limits of what enforced return policies can achieve, particularly in contexts where legal, political, diplomatic, or practical obstacles to return exist. These include statelessness, lack of identification documents, non-cooperation by countries of origin, and humanitarian considerations, such as illness or host country family life.

To contextualize the cross-national differences in non-return policies, we draw on the typology of post-arrival migration enforcement regimes developed by Leerkes and Van Houte (2020). These regimes are defined as clusters of policies and practices that structure how states manage the presence of irregular migrants following the rejection or expiration of legal stay. They result from a balancing of different state interests (security, economic growth, social fairness, rule of law) and capacities (bureaucratic, institutional, diplomatic, and legal). The typology identifies four ideal-typical enforcement regimes.

Thick enforcement regimes (e.g., Netherlands, Switzerland) are characterized by strong state capacity and a firm commitment to enforcement. These regimes emphasize formal control and the rule of law, often excluding irregular migrants from public services and enforcing return decisions rigorously. At the same

time, thick regimes are under pressure to address humanitarian and public order issues that partially arise because of the deliberate social exclusion of irregular migrants, leading to the development of controlled non-return mechanisms (e.g., LVV in the Netherlands or *Härtefallregelung* in Switzerland). These mechanisms typically offer limited reach and conditional rights.

Targeted enforcement regimes (e.g., historically Germany and Sweden) possess moderate to high enforcement capacities that are used selectively, with states often carving out legal niches for certain groups. Germany's use of the *Duldung* status, and its subsequent pathways to regularization for certain groups, and Sweden's program to allow rejected asylum seekers to stay if they have found a job in Sweden (Lindberg 2020, Emilsson 2014), illustrate a more targeted logic, wherein productive or integrated migrants are tolerated and eventually selectively incorporated into society and the labor market (with the prospect of permanent residency and naturalization). Recent trends suggest a shift toward a thicker regime, particularly in response to political pressures and changes in public opinion (Appleby, 2024).

Thin enforcement regimes (e.g., Italy and Spain) are characterized by limited capacity and relatively low enforcement interest. Thin regimes often tolerate irregular stay combining institutional abandonment and regularization programs as non-return policies. Italy has implemented multiple regularization campaigns. These arrangements may provide some measure of de facto inclusion but lack legal security and consistency, as regularized migrants may eventually fall back into irregularity.

Hampered enforcement regimes are marked by strong enforcement interest but limited capacity. Poland's regime, for instance, has certain aspects of a hampered regime as it lacks the administrative and diplomatic resources to return irregular migrants from some countries, especially non-European ones. This is likely to be among the reasons why it attempts to prevent entry through externalization and border enforcement, while also tolerating onward movement to Western Europe. It could be said that the Polish non-return policy consists of a kind of "double externalization": it keeps irregular migrants in non-EU transit countries, while also positioning itself as a transit country within the EU. At the same time, in the past, some groups of irregular migrants, especially Ukrainians, were largely tolerated. We thus observe a fragmented and inconsistent policy landscape, where a targeted logic – which in the case of Poland is oriented at selectively preventing entry among racialized groups in particular, rather than at selectively enforcing return – is combined with the informal toleration practices found in thin enforcement regimes (cf. Klaus & Szulecka, 2023).

Evaluating non-return policies: 'costs' and 'benefits'

Non-return policies affect the lives of individuals subject to them as well as the broader society through their economic and political implications. In our analysis of selected non-return policies in five European countries, we consider both perspectives (migrants and society/state) when assessing the costs and benefits of these policies along *three* key dimensions: human rights and capabilities, economic perspectives and political interests. We understand 'costs and benefits' in a broad sense as not only involving monetary costs and benefits, but also aspects related to individual capabilities or public acceptance

First, to help assess the costs and benefits for *migrants*, we employ the Capability Approach developed by Amartya Sen (1993, 2005) and further elaborated by Martha Nussbaum (2000, 2011). This approach centers on the actual freedoms individuals have to lead the lives they have reason to value. It moves

beyond formal rights and legal status to consider the real opportunities available to people in practice. From a capability-oriented perspective, non-return policies must be evaluated not only by their legal form or intent, but by their actual impact on migrants' substantive freedoms. Key capability indicators (Nussbaum 2011) include legal recognition and stability (e.g., policies that provide at least temporary documentation reduce legal insecurity and enable access to services), physical and mental health (e.g., access to healthcare, stable housing, and freedom from detention are prerequisites for well-being), education and employment opportunities (e.g., the ability to work legally and pursue education supports economic autonomy and social integration), and social participation and family life (e.g., rights to family unity and participation in community life underpin long-term belonging). Policies that restrict these capabilities – by confining migrants to detention, excluding them from labor markets, or placing them in legal limbo – undermine migrants' autonomy and violate the principle of human dignity. In contrast, policies like Germany's *Ausbildungsduldung* combine temporary legal status with integration measures, potentially supporting migrants' agency and social contributions.

Second, we consider economic costs and benefits. On the one hand, migrants may benefit from economic integration and opportunities that regularization policies offer, and can expand their freedom to pursue valued lives; conversely, restrictive measures such as denied access to the labor market tend to limit them. On the other hand, from the viewpoint of the deporting (or host) state, economic costs and benefits play a key role. For example, regularization policies that facilitate labor market access may yield substantial economic benefits, especially in tight labour markets. Regularized migrants can contribute to tax revenues, help fill labor shortages and reduce informal employment, while also contributing to improved health, financial independence, and reduced reliance on emergency services (cf. Kraler, 2019). Conversely, exclusionary policies (e.g., detention) are expensive and often ineffective (cf. Leerkes and Broeders, 2010; Leerkes & Kox, 2017). Moreover, they may lead to secondary costs, such as homelessness, illness, and marginalization, ultimately burdening local services and eroding public safety.

Third, we consider political costs and benefits. More inclusive non-return policies may face political resistance, especially if perceived to undermine border control or reward irregularity. Concerns about “pull factors” – despite being difficult to prove – and fairness to legal migrants can stand in the way of public support (Schultz, Wagner, & Allemann, 2018). However, exclusionary policies – particularly those involving detention without clear legal pathways – may provoke legal challenges, human rights criticism, and public resistance. Moreover policies that violate human rights or severely limit migrants' capabilities may also be politically costly in liberal states that have signed various conventions on human rights, and where parts of the population may protest against migrants rights being violated, which often happens when exclusionary practices affect migrants in people's personal networks (e.g. via schools, communities, work places) (Ambrosini, 2016; Castañeda, 2010; Leerkes, Varsanyi and Engbersen, 2012). Still exclusionary policies can have a deterrent effect and show that the state has control over migration. This deterrent effect is however not easy to prove and often argued in the policy making domain.

Toward promising practices

In order to preserve their legitimacy, liberal states need to balance different interests, or ‘functional requirements’, in their migration policies (also see Boswell, 2007). This is also true in the field of migrant return. Promising non-return policies need to strike the right balance between different interests at stake: ideally, they should contribute to migrants' capabilities, be economically beneficial, and politically feasible. In identifying “promising” non-return policies, our framework thus highlights those that are:

- Relatively inclusive: rights-based, enabling access to essential services and promoting migrant capabilities, while, ideally, also having a considerable reach or be scalable
- Cost-effective, in both economic and social terms
- Politically feasible (e.g. have sufficient public support and respect fundamental rights)

Non-return policies such as the vocational toleration and other integration or labor-based regularization mechanisms in Germany, large-scale regularization programs in Italy, the LVV in the Netherlands, the *Härtefallregelung* in Switzerland and the permits to stay based on respect for family life and children's rights in Poland seem to harbor at least certain elements of this model. We will therefore zoom in on the characteristics and documented outcomes of these programs.

METHODOLOGY

Case selection

The analysis of promising non-return policies comprises several case studies in five EU+ countries: Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, Poland and Switzerland. As was explained in the previous section, the five selected countries vary in terms of their regional positionality within Europe, their deportation regimes (Leerkes and van Houte, 2020) and their approaches to non-return. Selecting five countries allowed us to compare a wide range of policies, while considering the question of potential policy transferability. In the five countries, we selected different cases for analysis: two regularization mechanisms in Germany, the 2020 regularization program in Italy, the hardship regulation in Switzerland, a temporary measure in the Netherlands and a permission to stay for humanitarian reasons and 'conventions-related' temporary residence permits in Poland.

Data collection

In Germany, Italy, Poland and the Netherlands, primary data was collected between September 2024 and June 2025 through 60 qualitative, semi-structured interviews, and four national multi-stakeholder roundtables. For an in-depth analysis of existing non-return policies from a multi-actor perspective, we conducted interviews with 10 employers, 30 migrants with different (ir)regularized statuses as well as various public and non-public actors (including NGOs, lawyers and immigration authorities). A list of respondents can be found in the appendix. In Switzerland, data collection primarily occurred through document analysis and analysis of secondary data, as will be detailed below.

All interviews were semi-structured and followed the structure of previously designed questions. We designed different interview guides for migrants, employers and other stakeholders; the interview guides comprised similar, overarching topics which were adapted according to the respondent, country context and particular policy. Respondents were, for instance, asked to reflect upon their personal experiences with 'irregularity' and existing non-return policies (as employer, migrant or stakeholder), policies' benefits and costs, support infrastructures and networks, or the legitimacy of policies in times of increased politicization of the topic of non-return.

More specifically, interviews with (ir)regularized migrants were aimed at understanding how migrants experienced their irregular stay in their country of residence, and why/how they accessed pathways to legality or other provisions to accommodate their situation of non-return. We were moreover interested in gaining deeper insights into potential obstacles to accessing regularization, or other rights and

resources, the role of intermediaries, as well as their contact with authorities and ‘the law’. Interviews with employers focused on their experience hiring (ir)regularized migrants, their role as employers in facilitating regularization, and their personal evaluation of non-return policies and their effect on employed migrants. Lastly, interviews with other stakeholders who supported (ir)regularized migrants or were responsible for the issuance of permits provided a meta-perspective that helped contextualize individual experiences of migrants (and employers) and give more insights on the broader institutional and policy context.

In addition to the interviews, a series of roundtable discussions were conducted as a second layer of primary data collection. These roundtables were designed to bring together diverse stakeholders, including representatives from NGOs, employers, migration law experts, and various levels of government, to collectively reflect on key themes related to non-return policies and to critically evaluate what are often referred to as “promising policies”. Between December 2024 and June 2025, four national-level roundtables were held, numbers of participants ranging between four and thirty. The discussions were guided by a detailed outline that included topics such as the governance of irregular migration, the feasibility and sustainability of alternative policies, the goals of such policies, their accessibility and impact, and the conditions under which such policies could be transferred to other contexts. Human rights considerations, as well as broader discourses such as economic rationales were also addressed.

The roundtables were intended not only to gather additional perspectives but also to foster exchange among actors directly involved in migration policy. Participants were selected based on their expertise and roles in implementation, advocacy or as employer, ensuring that a variety of strategic and operational views were represented. In this way, the roundtables provided a collective, practice-oriented dimension that complemented the individual narratives that emerged from the interviews, allowing for a richer and more nuanced understanding of how non-return policies are framed, experienced, and contested in different contexts.

Ethical considerations

Given the sensitivity of the topic and the precarious situations of many irregular migrants, it was crucial to approach interviews with care and reflexivity, particularly regarding power dynamics between researchers and participants (Bryman 2016; Fedyuk & Zentai 2018). Many respondents may have experienced trauma, legal uncertainty, and limited autonomy due to their dependence on external support (Doná 2007; Eastmond 2007). Trust, sensitivity, and the awareness of the responsibility as a researcher – also regarding potential consequences of the research for the participants – were therefore central elements of the research process. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, methods, and data handling. This information served as the basis for their informed and voluntary consent regarding their participation in the research (Mackenzie et al. 2007; Vervliet *et al.* 2015). Many respondents preferred giving verbal consent and preferred notes taking over audio-recording. All participants were informed about the anonymization strategy of the project and were encouraged to respond only to questions they felt comfortable with. Where deemed necessary or possible, additional information on supporting organizations was provided to the respondents (e.g., when questions regarding their legal status or procedure arose during the interview). Finally, while researchers could not always address participants' immediate needs, the working paper seeks to highlight migrants' perspectives and experiences, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the situation of (ir)regularized migrants in Europe.

Data collection in the selected countries

Germany

In Germany, data collection was conducted between September 2024 and June 2025 in the regional state of Baden-Württemberg (BW), combining semi-structured interviews with a multi-stakeholder roundtable discussion in March 2025. BW served as a strategic location for the analysis of non-return policies due to the regional state's strong economy, an active employer network lobbying for migrants' rights to stay, and relatively inclusive integration policies which seem to provide rejected asylum seekers with promising opportunities to regularize, in particular due to the region's growing labor shortage.

A total of 22 interviews were carried out: ten interviews with migrants (two women, eight men), six with employers, three with NGOs, one with a legal expert and two with representatives of regional and local authorities in BW. The stakeholder respondents were purposefully selected due to their professional background and expertise (e.g., as employees of a local support organization) or because they had hired refugees/supported migrants during their regularization procedure. Among the interviewed companies were a large regional energy provider, a medium-sized IT company, a care organization, and three smaller craft skilled businesses (bakery, brewery, carpenter), located in different parts of BW. The owner of the brewery is also the founder of a regional company network which lobbies for refugees' right to stay (also for those without a residence permit).

Migrants were approached via existing personal contacts (the researcher had previously worked in Stuttgart), employers or support organizations. Interviews were conducted in public spaces (local libraries or café) or in the offices of support organizations; eight interviews were conducted in German, two in English. The interviewed migrants come from various countries (Iraq, Afghanistan, Turkey, Sri Lanka, Kosovo, Togo, Nigeria and Kameron) and had lived in Germany between three and nine years. Interviewed migrants had already regularized or had the intention/prospect to regularize via two main regularization mechanisms – one 'qualification pathway' (vocational toleration, §19d) and one 'integration pathway' (§25a, §25b, §104c). At the time of the interviews, all respondents worked, followed a vocational training or a study program as most of them were able to regularize due to having work, following a vocational training or being considered 'well-integrated'. The specificities of the two pathways will be explained in the empirical section.

Interviews were fully transcribed using the software Amberscript, and coded by the researcher, using a concept-driven and data-driven coding approach. That is, concept-driven codes (mostly based on the interview guide and the 'cost-benefit' analysis) were subsequently complemented by 'data-driven' codes (codes emerging from the data more inductively). In addition to the interviews, a two-hour round table was organized in Stuttgart with the participation of representatives from the public sector and civil society organizations as well as employers. The discussion offered broader insights into advantages and disadvantages of existing regularization pathways in Germany, practical obstacles regarding the implementation of legal regulations, and concrete policy recommendations.

The Netherlands

The fieldwork on the National Alien Services (*Landelijke Vreemdelingen Voorzieningen*, LVV) in The Netherlands included 11 interviews and one roundtable with various stakeholders. The LVV was implemented in 5 Dutch cities. We interviewed representatives from 4 of them: Rotterdam, Groningen, Amsterdam, and Utrecht, only Eindhoven was not included. The interview participants comprised the

central government, municipalities and NGOs. In addition to institutional viewpoints, we also captured in the interviews the lived experiences, aspirations and difficulties of migrants within the LVV and also of those that fell outside of the program. Six interviews were conducted online and five took place in person.

As part of the fieldwork, we organized a stakeholder roundtable, which brought together representatives from the central government, municipalities, NGOs and academia. This roundtable was conducted as part of the LVV Final Conference organized in The Hague.¹ The roundtable provided a valuable forum for cross-institutional dialogue on objectives, outcomes and ways forward of the LVV.

Italy

The qualitative fieldwork conducted in Italy combined semi-structured interviews with a multi-stakeholder roundtable discussion. A total of 18 interviews were carried out: 13 with migrants who applied for regularization (9 under the 2020 scheme mainly aimed at the care-related employment sector, 3 under the 1998 scheme, and 1 under the 2002 scheme), 4 with employers, and 1 with a representative from a local trade office. A snowball sampling method was used to recruit both migrants and employers, given the informal and often opaque nature of domestic and care work arrangements. The fieldwork presented several challenges, particularly in identifying employers who had directly hired migrants. This difficulty is closely linked to the sponsorship-based structure of the regularization process, in which employers are required to submit the application on behalf of the migrant. As a result, it was often difficult to distinguish between genuine and potentially fictitious employer participation in the process. Furthermore, many potential interviewees were elderly and unable to participate, while others delegated communication to family members who were unavailable or unwilling to speak.

In addition to the interviews, a roundtable was organized with the participation of representatives from both the public sector and civil society organizations. This discussion offered broader insights into the governance of regularization measures, the practical challenges of implementation, and the perspectives of actors working directly with irregular migrants. The roundtable helped contextualize individual experiences within institutional dynamics and highlighted the tensions between policy objectives and on-the-ground realities.

Poland

In Poland, two kinds of data were collected. First, in-depth individual interviews were conducted to better understand the situation of people having no possibility or unwillingness to return to their country, and at the same time have limited opportunities to obtain or prolong a regular legal residence status in Poland. Interviews were conducted with actors who support migrants exposed to return orders, on both commercial (two lawyers) or free of charge bases (one expert leading an NGO supporting migrants) or have expertise in the legal and institutional framework of migrant work in Poland (one expert representing employers' organization). Three interviews were conducted with migrants who have had experience of irregular stay in Poland and who have been involved in paid work in Poland (one woman from Ukraine was regularized based on short-term residence permit issued in very specific circumstances; one man from Senegal who is awaiting the possibility to legalize his stay, and one woman from Kazakhstan who was granted a permission to stay for humanitarian reasons, after a number of negative

¹ Since the LVV program ceased operations on January 1, 2025, a final conference was organized to formally conclude its activities and assess its overall impact. As part of this conference, we hosted a stakeholder roundtable to reflect on the goals the program was intended to achieve.

decisions in asylum procedure). Individual interviews were conducted between February 2025 and June 2025.

The second method used to collect data on non-return policies was a roundtable organized on April 2, 2025, engaging a diverse group of nine participants with expertise in migration control, migration law, legal aid provided to migrants as well as commercial services offered to migrants. Experts participating in the focus group discussion represented public administration, civil society, and academia. Three of the participants, besides their involvement in academic work or civil society, work also as commercial immigration lawyers. The discussion was held in Polish, and it was moderated by legal scholars researching Polish migration law in practice. To allow participation of experts representing various regions, the roundtable was organized in an online format. The idea for sampling experts was to combine perspectives of those who are involved in drafting provisions related to migration, in legality checks and issuance of return decisions, in providing legal aid to migrants on non-profit bases as well as in providing commercial services to migrants.

All participants of the qualitative study were selected deliberately – the main criterion determining the selection was the expertise in or – in case of migrants – lived experience of possible ways in or out of irregularity, especially in the context of the labour market. All interviews but one and the roundtable discussion were recorded, transcribed and translated from Polish to English. One interview was conducted in English and French, and it was not recorded. The notes were taken in English.

Switzerland

The case study on the Swiss regularization mechanism (*Härtefallregelung*) is based on an analysis of primary legal sources such as the Aliens Act and Asylum Act as well as national and cantonal guidelines to the regularization mechanism. The analysis of these primary sources is complemented by extensive literature research, including both academic publications and grey literature. In addition, the analysis draws selectively on insights from a limited number of expert interviews and written statements conducted primarily for other work packages of FAiR. These include cantonal migration offices involved in the application of the *Härtefallregelung* as well as from close observers, including representatives of UNHCR Switzerland and the Swiss Refugee Council.

ASSESSING NON-RETURN POLICIES – EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Germany

I. Promising non-return policies in Germany

For the analysis and assessment of existing non-return policies in Germany, this section focuses on two explicit *regularization mechanisms* for tolerated individuals in Germany. A toleration status (*Duldung*) is granted to individuals with a return order, such as rejected asylum seekers, whose deportation is *temporarily* suspended (for instance because of missing travel documents or health-related reasons; publication of the German Parliament no. 19/12502 2019).

The first regularization mechanism, **Pathway A**, has a strong **labor-related focus** and is based on following vocational training (as means of *qualification*; §60c) or having *qualified* employment (§19d) as a route to legal residence. The *Ausbildungsduldung* (vocational toleration) falls under this labor-related regularization pathway and ensures that deportation is suspended during the training period (usually up

to three years). Individuals who are granted a vocational toleration under §60c for the purpose of training can subsequently apply for a temporary residence permit under §19d once they have successfully completed their vocational training and have found qualified employment.

The second regularization mechanism, **Pathway B**, centers more broadly on **integration achievements**, including, but not limited to, (unqualified) employment, the acquisition of a school degree, basic knowledge of the legal and social system and the way of life in Germany, and the “commitment to the free democratic basic order of the Federal Republic of Germany” (Residence Act, §25a, §25b). Importantly, pathway B does not focus on ‘qualified’ employment but offers opportunities to ‘well-integrated foreigners’ who are able or *expected* to ensure their subsistence by “pursuing an economic activity” (Residence Act, §25b). The recently introduced *Chancenaufenthalt* (Opportunity Residence permit; §104c) falls under this integration-related regularization pathway; this temporary residence permit is granted for 18 months and offers opportunities for tolerated foreigners, who have lived in Germany without interruption for five years after 31.10.2017, to ‘work’ toward meeting the requirements for a more permanent status. Individuals who, within this period, are able to meet additional requirements – such as demonstrating basic German language skills, verifying their identity, and proving that they can primarily support themselves through an ‘economic activity’ – may subsequently switch to a residence permit under §25a (for well-integrated young adults) or §25b (for well-integrated adults). If they are unable to fulfil these integration-related requirements, they ‘fall back’ into toleration.

Both regularization mechanisms require a certain period of residence in Germany, a “verified identity”, a clean criminal record, and a toleration status prior to regularization to indicate the completion of the asylum procedure. Importantly, individuals have the opportunity to apply for permanent residency or naturalization later on, contingent on fulfilling the necessary requirements. Moreover, spouses and children of individuals holding regularized statuses may also be granted the same residence permit.

II. Objectives of regularization pathways in Germany/Baden-Württemberg

In Germany, the abovementioned regularization mechanisms are referred to as “**prospects of staying**” or “**residence prospects**” (*Bleibeperspektiven*). Their objective is to offer tolerated people – who fulfill a wide range of requirements – an opportunity to legalize their residence and gain a permanent right to stay. According to Florian Hassler, State Secretary for Political Coordination and European Affairs at the State Ministry in Baden-Württemberg, these residence prospects serve a ‘triple objective’: they address public order concerns, respond to humanitarian considerations, and meet labor market needs.

“The regulations ensure that those refugees who have been living here for many years, speak German, are well integrated, have a job, and support themselves can obtain a permanent right to stay. This is not only a matter of humanity, but also clearly in our country’s best interest in light of an increasing shortage of skilled labor.” (Staatsministerium Baden-Württemberg, press release, 2022).

The latter objective is strongly reflected in Pathway A (regularization through qualification), in particular the vocational toleration which was introduced after the ‘long summer of migration’ as a way to ensure that also tolerated individuals with a rejected asylum claim could secure their stay (temporarily) while following a vocational training. In Baden-Württemberg, companies lobbied for people’s right to stay (independent of their (asylum) status), in line with the principle “who works and is integrated, should be allowed to stay” (Baden-Württemberg press release, 2022; also mentioned in various interviews with employers). A representative of the regional authority responsible for the issuance, termination and extension of individuals’ toleration status (*Regierungspräsidium*) similarly stated that “*it is not our intention to deport someone who may have the opportunity to legalize their stay.*” Pathway B

(regularization through integration) also falls under the “residence prospects” and centers on a wide range of integration achievements to grant tolerated individuals access to legal residence. The objective of pathway A is to offer long-term solutions to well-integrated individuals whose deportation has been suspended for four to six years. In general, these regulations are seen as means of preventing or ending long-term irregularity in which individuals become trapped in a loop of indefinite ‘chain tolerations.’

The importance of leaving the toleration status behind was also mentioned in several interviews, where respondents reflected on their personal experiences of irregularity – marked by a sense of being in “standstill” and a constant fear of deportation. A man from Kameron, who came to Germany in 2018 and still seeks a way to regularize, noted that *“people have gone crazy because of the system, because they sit at home, have nothing to do, feel isolated and have no perspective. This leads to problems in the head.”*

III. Analysis of outcomes

a. Number of beneficiaries

When analyzing current trends for Germany², we see that the number of individuals with a toleration status declined significantly, from 242.029 in 2021 to 178.512 in 2024. While the vocational toleration (§60c) saw consistent and marked decreases (from 7.736 to 2.747 in the same period), the Opportunity Residence permit (§104c) has become a major, albeit temporary, regularization channel, accounting for 49.263 by 2024. Moreover, the number of individuals granted residence based on “good integration” (Pathway B) increased steadily, from 25.114 in 2021 to 67.433 in 2024 – nearly tripling over three years. Though smaller in scale, the number of migrants regularized through the qualification route (§19d) also rose, from 6.087 in 2021 to 10.139 in 2024 (including people who previously had a vocational toleration).

Much like the national trend, Baden-Württemberg has seen a marked shift from toleration toward regular residence, especially since 2023. The introduction of §104c and the growing use of integration-based permits have played a central role in this transformation. More specifically, the total number of individuals with a toleration status declined from 34.360 in December 2021 to 23.487 in December 2024 (by almost 32%). The vocational toleration (§60c) saw consistent decreases by almost 70% (from 1.357 in 2021 to 421 in 2024), while the Opportunity Residence permit (§104c) has become an important regularization channel in BW (accounting for 6099 individuals in 2024). Similar to the overall trend in Germany, the number of individuals granted residence based on “good integration” (Pathway B) almost tripled over three years. The number of migrants who regularized through the qualification route rose slightly from 1.265 in 2021 to 2.128 in 2024. By the end of 2024, more than 17.500 individuals held a regularized status, compared to almost 23.500 tolerated individuals.

² Sources: Bundestag Drucksache 20/1048, Drucksache 20/5870, Drucksache 20/1110, Drucksache 20/192. Presented numbers include residence permits granted to spouses and children.

Figure 1: Numbers of regularizations vis-à-vis number of tolerations in BW 2021 - 2024

While regularization mechanisms in Germany are considered selective due to narrow and numerous requirements (see also above), their **reach** is still significant when compared to the overall number of tolerated persons and the growing significance of (temporary) regularization pathways over the past four years. Nonetheless, there is still a large number of persons who are excluded from existing regulations, suggesting obstacles in accessibility – as will be discussed below. In terms of **rights allocation** the existing mechanisms seem to fare rather well as they grant regularized individuals access to welfare benefits and shelter, work and education, and, importantly, more legal security for themselves as well as their spouses and children. While most regularized statuses also provide the opportunity for long-term stay and eventually naturalization, the Opportunity Residence Act grants residence for a relatively short time, posing the risk of continued irregularity. Finally, the analyzed mechanisms can be described as **explicit non-return policies** as they formally acknowledge protracted situations of non-return and are explicitly framed as “prospects to stay” within official discourse and legal frameworks. These regulations thus are explicitly designed to address the situation of ‘non-removable’ migrants whose deportation has been suspended for multiple years and who show the willingness and ability to work and integrate.

b. Cost-benefit analysis

Individual costs and benefits

Migrants interviewed for this study generally evaluated existing opportunities for regularization as positive. For those who successfully regularized, their lives changed significantly, or as a young engineering student from Iraq put it: “*You are suddenly a free human, you are no longer an illegal person [...], you can go anywhere*” (D-M-7). Respondents identified various **benefits** of regularization: an increased sense of security, the possibility of traveling (within Germany, abroad, to visit family) and a new sense of freedom and independence (D-M-4, D-M-5, D-M-7). Respondents highlighted that regularizing meant leaving a legal limbo situation and a constant fear of deportation behind; they now felt more secure and relieved which also had a positive effect on their mental health (also mentioned by support organizations). Moreover, a legal residence guaranteed more access to rights, resources and choices, including the possibility to switch work more easily, request study financing, or, eventually, apply for permanent residency and naturalization. Finally, successful regularization was also seen as an expression of empowerment and capability (social worker; D-M-4, D-M-5, D-M-7).

Besides the *Ausbildungsduldung* and the residence permit for well-integrated juveniles and young adults (§25a), respondents also described the new Opportunity Residence permit as an “effective instrument” to address situations of non-return and “save a significant number from continued chain tolerations” (roundtable discussion). According to migrants, the new regulation in fact introduced an unexpected opportunity previously not available, changing their lives significantly.

Interviewed migrants also identified various **costs** and obstacles with regards to regularization. First, existing opportunities may **constrain people’s capabilities and their freedom of choice** regarding their career paths. Respondents mentioned that their choice of vocational training was greatly influenced by their desire to secure their stay which is why they often opted for vocational trainings that seemed more easily accessible (nurse, craftsman): *“You just look for something — anything — as long as it’s a training program, because the main goal is to be able to stay here.”* (D-M-7) This strategic behavior often came at the cost of personal aspirations and was also viewed critically by employers. Moreover, the close link between employment or vocational training and regularization often created dependencies and enormous pressure, making it difficult for migrants to change employer or leave their training programs.

Second, respondents also drew attention to the **selective nature of existing pathways**.³ Persons who are likely to achieve regularization are typically capital- or resource-rich. They tend to speak the German language well and have some form of education or qualification – or the capacity to acquire them quickly (cultural capital). They typically have supportive social networks (social capital), possess financial means to access legal support, or language courses (economic capital), and are generally viewed as “well-integrated” (symbolic capital; Jonitz & Leerkes, 2022). Moreover, existing pathways are more easily accessible to younger and healthy migrants. Finally, a person’s nationality may also influence their chances of regularizing because *“some people [from Turkey or Georgia] are now quickly being sent back home”* (social worker), leaving little opportunity to learn the language and ‘qualifying’ for a vocational training and regularization later on.

Third, even with a regularized status, some **uncertainty remains** as *“you are never totally safe from deportation”* (respondent from Kameron). Regarding the Residence Opportunity Act respondents stated that it is often unclear what comes after. According to a respondent from the Refugee Council in Stuttgart, *“it is still difficult to estimate how many people will be able to transition to a subsequent residence status and how many will fall back into a tolerated stay. 18 months can pass very quickly — the risk is definitely there.”* Moreover, the Opportunity Residence Act is only in effect until 31.12.2025 and only applicable to people who have lived in Germany for at least five years as of the reference date 31.10.2022, thus representing only a temporary solution. Finally, from a short-term perspective - before actual regularization – migrants experienced various **obstacles** related to the **legal and bureaucratic system**, and may experience **heightened fears of deportation** because of the need to share information about their identity to the authorities, as discussed in the next section.

Societal costs and benefits

Economic aspects

Germany faces a significant shortage of skilled labor. Providing (rejected) asylum seekers, including those with a tolerated stay, an opportunity to stay through employment or vocational training is considered by

³ Arguably, the Opportunity Residence Act is less selective as it offers a (temporary) regularization opportunity to those without formal qualification or language skills.

many respondents as a **“win-win-win” situation**: *“We [companies] need people, it helps us, it helps the state, it helps the refugees as they can work full-time.”* (D-E-4) Existing regularization pathways benefit employers because they allow them to hire (rejected) asylum seekers by promising more legal security and ensuring – at least in theory – that their employees will not be deported. Interviewed employers see regularization opportunities as complementary and “important recruiting tool” (D-E-3) and as a means to respond to the persistent shortage of (un)skilled workers, by drawing on an already present workforce.

Besides benefitting employers, regularization opportunities also benefit the state as they *“ease the burden on public authorities, accommodation facilities, and the social welfare system”* (municipal officer). Moreover, by creating pathways to legality through employment and integration, the state signals to society that it *“takes action”* (legal expert) and actively responds to the situation of non-return. Labor- and integration-related regularization opportunities thus appear to fill (some) protection and enforcement gaps, while also paying attention to current labor market dynamics.

Despite seeing the importance and necessity of hiring (tolerated) migrants and refugees, employers also pointed to various **obstacles**. Smaller companies reported that hiring refugees and migrants requires substantial time, money and effort, with local infrastructures often providing insufficient information and support for both companies and migrants. Decreasing numbers of German language courses were seen as an additional challenge, directly affecting the employability of (tolerated) migrants (roundtable discussion and interviews). Some employers also noted that existing regularization opportunities mainly target ‘skilled’ persons (*Fachkräfte*), offering fewer options and security for ‘unskilled’ workers (*Arbeitskräfte*), despite a clear economic need. Regularization opportunities that do not ask for a completed school or permits vocational training or qualified work often require lengthy periods of residence, making access to these pathways more difficult (five years for §104c and six years for §25b).

Finally, employers expressed concerns regarding the perceived arbitrariness of tolerated migrants’ job search. They felt that some of them primarily choose to apply for a job or vocational training at their company because of the pressure to secure their stay and not because they were necessarily passionate about the actual profession. Other companies reported having difficulties retaining staff or finding trainees as their requirements were too high and people seek ‘easier’ jobs to secure their stay. A representative of a regional energy provider explains: *“Some wanted to become technicians but ended up becoming carpenters—simply because they needed a training position quickly.”*

Political aspects

Some respondents noted that existing regularization opportunities are **societally and politically accepted** due to their emphasis on integration and employment. According to some employers, “even the CDU [conservative Christian party]” and critical parts of the population support these regulations because of the various, promised societal benefits (eased financial burden on the welfare state, promotion of long-term integration, incentives for regular employment, and stability for individuals). Yet, while regularization pathways appear(ed) to enjoy general public and political support, various respondents raised concerns about the shifting political and societal climate that is growing increasingly hostile to migrants. Conflicting narratives at the political level – stressing the importance of migration to address labor shortages vs. calls for a harder grip on irregular migration – create insecurities among societal actors, employers and migrants alike. Various respondents pointed out that the pressure to increase deportation numbers has led to “the wrong people being deported because these are the ones they can find” (D-E-4) since they go to work regularly and are visible to authorities. They further pointed out that

lacking political attention to the topic at both the national and the regional level may have a detrimental effect on employers' willingness to employ (rejected) asylum seekers and tolerated persons due to legal insecurities.

Somewhat contrary to the expressed concerns regarding crumbling societal or political support and an (over)emphasis on deportation, a regional official explained that from a government perspective, there lies a "big focus on the right to stay" for those who fulfil the requirements (D-GOV-1). When the new Opportunity Residence Act was introduced in 2022, the regional authority proactively informed all tolerated persons who were eligible for the opportunity residence permit. Also, local immigration authorities are supposed to offer consultation when the residency times for §25a and §25b are met. However, they do not always consistently fulfill their duty to inform (D-NGO-3).

Moreover, respondents consistently expressed frustration with the legal and administrative structures they were required to navigate. First, **continuous legal reforms** in the German Residence Act pose challenges for local and regional authorities as familiarizing themselves with legal changes requires substantial time, effort and training. Given the current shortage of staff in most local immigration authorities, this appears to exacerbate an already strenuous situation in an "overburdened" system. Also, for other actors supporting refugees or tolerated persons, frequent legal changes and increased complexity made it difficult to "keep up".

Second, **contradictions** within the law complicate decision-making processes, also for local immigration authorities confronted with the balancing act to decide if a law should be used to restrict or enable residence (N-GOV-1). The Refugee Council's representative similarly notes that ambiguous policy goals pose challenges for caseworkers as it is often unclear whether legal regulations – such as §25b – are intended as tools for migration control or as mechanisms to grant a right to stay, leaving room for interpretation and discretion. As a result, implementation varies locally (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2023). Highlighting the significant influence of authorities, a respondent from Kameron stated that authorities "*are like a king, you do not see them, but you fear them*".

Third, another frequently mentioned dilemma is the obligation to verify one's identity, ideally through passport procurement. While a '**verified identity**' is needed for regularization, people also fear that they may increase their deportability by providing identification documents – as the reason for their suspended deportation is often related to missing travel documents. A social worker explains that applying for regularization involves a certain risk; in her work, she is often confronted with the question: "*How can we create trust in authorities when cooperation can also lead to deportation?*" Since 2019, a 'verified identity' has become even more important: individuals applying for a vocational toleration must have had their identity verified within the first six months after their arrival in Germany, long before they potentially apply for the vocational toleration. Regularization may fail if individuals do not cooperate in a timely manner with the clarification of identity (D-GOV-1; legal expert). The new Opportunity Residence Act seems to partially address this dilemma because it can be granted without a verified identity and offers the opportunity to provide identification documents without the threat of immediate deportation.

Fourth, almost all respondents voiced their dissatisfaction with the **lengthy regularization procedures** due to legal complexity and slow bureaucracy, requiring significant resources, effort and time from employers, supporting organizations and volunteers. Respondents compared the bureaucratic system to a labyrinth in which chaos prevails and where the "*left hand does not know what the right hand does, and both do not know what the head thinks*" (D-E-5). Social workers also pointed out that individual cases

usually require a high level of guidance and the collaboration of multiple actors to ensure a successful outcome of the procedure. This shows, yet again, that regularization is resource-heavy – both in terms of individual resources necessary to meet requirements, but also in terms of supporting actors’ resources (time, money, human resources) necessary to navigate the complex legal environment.

Finally, respondents pointed to the perceived inaccessibility and lack of transparency of local immigration authorities. A local service provider compared the authorities to “Fort Knox” to underline the notion that authorities were hard to reach and that it was difficult to impossible to understand “what is going on inside”. Long waiting times for appointments and a general delay in the issuance or renewal of residence permits further fueled fear, insecurity, and mistrust. In some instances, such bureaucratic delays put people’s jobs and vocational trainings at risk, creating more insecurity for both migrants and employers. Authorities thus become a “bottleneck” (round table discussion; *Nadelöhr*) – a narrow and restrictive passage that created a hurdle for people trying to regularize.

Notably, in various conversations respondents also drew on the notion of “luck” to explain why they were able to successfully regularize. Two young men from Iraq and Afghanistan noted that they were “lucky” that they were minors when arriving in Germany as this gave them access to a more extensive support network. Others also described being “lucky” because they met a volunteer or family who supported them throughout the process or an employer who was willing to vouch for them.

Human rights

The discussed regularization mechanisms provide **access to fundamental rights** such as shelter, financial support and access to work and education. However, a legal expert notes that migrants should be given more than ‘just the bare minimum’ and expressed concerns regarding the increasingly dehumanizing discourse related to (irregular) migration in Germany. Most regularization pathways generally allow individuals to apply for permanent residency and, eventually, citizenship, granting full legal access. However, some **pathways remain insecure** (§104c), leaving individuals at risk to fall back into irregularity, which may also adversely affect their mental health. This ongoing insecurity is exemplified by personal accounts, such as a young man from Afghanistan who has been waiting for nine years to regularize, despite seemingly fulfilling all requirements (D-M-3).

The previously outlined **selectivity** poses significant challenges, particularly for older, ill, traumatized, or disabled individuals struggling to meet the strict requirements of language proficiency, employment, and qualifications (social worker, roundtable discussion). This utilitarian perspective results in a “brutal categorization” and exclusion of those deemed undesired (N-NGO-3):

“The current prospects for staying are very utilitarian, with a strong selection between the desired ones who are young, healthy and able to work, and the undesired ones who are old, not healthy, and are not able to work. From the perspective of the Refugee Council, this strong categorization and selection is an act of violence and exclusion that is reflected in a brutal manner.”

On a positive note, a recent legal reform (2024) changed the provision so that individuals with toleration status *should* now be granted employment permits. This means that in principle tolerated persons are allowed to work (with exceptions for those from safe countries or those who do not cooperate in obtaining passports face employment bans and receive a so-called ‘Duldung light’).

Summary

The in-depth analysis of explicit regularization mechanisms for tolerated migrants in Germany highlights a range of individual and societal costs and benefits, shaped by both short- and long-term dynamics. On the individual level, regularization offers a critical exit from legal limbo, enhancing security, mobility, mental health, and access to rights such as work, education, and eventual permanent residency. Pathways like the vocational toleration (§60c) and integration-based (§25a/b) permits are generally perceived as meaningful, enabling individuals' capabilities and their freedom to shape their own lives. However, some of these benefits are offset by high entry thresholds and selectivity. Legal status is often contingent on language proficiency, verified identity, and continuous employment, creating dependencies that can also restrict personal and professional capabilities. The process itself is bureaucratically complex, resource-intensive, and marked by uncertainty and certain risks (related to identity verification), especially for vulnerable individuals or those without strong support networks. Yet, despite their selective nature, non-return policies in Germany/BW still have a significant reach when compared to the overall number of tolerated persons, and regularized individuals are granted substantial rights. At the societal level, regularization contributes to addressing labor shortages, supporting long-term integration, and easing the 'burden' on social welfare systems. Employers view these mechanisms as pragmatic tools for workforce stabilization. Nonetheless, the system imposes significant administrative burdens, particularly on small businesses, and remains selective, often excluding those deemed less 'useful' in economic (or societal) terms. While supported when framed around work and integration, the system's utilitarian orientation also raises concerns about fairness, accessibility, and long-term sustainability.

Considering the identified costs and benefits, the two pathways to regularization can be described as relatively promising non-return policies. They appear to yield important societal and economic benefits, respect basic human rights, and enable capabilities (albeit with certain restrictions). They also seem politically feasible due to likely public acceptance related to their labour- and integration-oriented character. However, recent shifts towards greater enforcement and deportation may undermine these policies' goals of providing long-term prospects for 'well-integrated' working individuals, as they risk being caught up in the grinding wheels of an increasingly restrictive approach to irregular migration.

The Netherlands

I. Promising non-return policies in The Netherlands

Several non-return accommodation policies exist in The Netherlands for individuals who cannot be returned which are based on humanitarian reasons: medical, family or impossibility to obtain travel documents.⁴ The Netherlands has developed a mechanism for implementing those non-return policies, the LVV (Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorzieningen, or National Facilities for Irregular Migrants).

The LVV was a pilot project funded by the central government and implemented in five cities in the Netherlands: Amsterdam, Utrecht, Rotterdam, Eindhoven and Groningen. The project ran for 5 years between 2019 to 2024. In October 2024 the central government decided to stop its funding citing the need to prioritize increasing returns over providing shelter to individuals without a legal right to remain in the Netherlands (Rijksoverheid 2024). The LVV was designed to provide a coordinated support network

⁴ For a mapping of these alternatives, see Ince Beqo and others (2024), Inventory of existing alternatives to return policies, FAiR working paper, available at: <https://fair-return.org/working-paper-inventory-of-existing-alternative-to-returns-policies/>.

for irregular migrants, including rejected asylum seekers, overstayers, stateless, etc. It brought together municipalities and national government institutions, such as the DT&V (Departure and Repatriation Centre), AVIM (Department of Immigration, Identification and Human Trafficking) which is part of the police, and IND (Immigration and Naturalization Service), alongside national and local NGOs, to help individuals find ‘sustainable solutions’ to their irregular status. These solutions could include return, regularization, or onward migration, depending on each person’s situation. The program offered shelter, social and legal counselling and support accessing medical care.

Beyond these essential support services, the LVV also introduced a shift in perspective regarding return. While a return decision formally remained the endpoint, the LVV created space to review legal cases and explore possibilities for regularization. In some municipalities, return was pursued only after all viable legal options to remain in the Netherlands had been exhausted (NL_MUN_1). By contrast, the central government viewed the LVV primarily as a form of shelter and counseling support intended to give migrants the time and space to reflect on and plan their return (Mack et al. 2022). Importantly, the LVV did not create *new* legal pathways for regularization. Instead, it supported the implementation of existing policies and helped individuals access procedures that were already available under Dutch law.

II. Objectives of the LVV in The Netherlands

The LVV program built on the earlier *Bed, Bath, and Bread* (BBB) initiative, which was introduced by Dutch municipalities in 2015 to provide basic shelter, food, and hygiene facilities to irregular migrants living on the streets (Hajer et al. 2024). In 2019, the central government launched the LVV as a follow-up initiative. According to the LVV Program Plan (2018), the central government and the participating municipalities defined the program’s main goal as *finding sustainable solutions* for migrants who lack legal residence status and are not entitled to national reception services. The LVV program aims to guide these individuals toward voluntary return, onward migration, or the regularization of their residence status.

An implicit objective of the LVV program was to reduce the societal problems linked to irregular migration, including homelessness, delinquency, and illnesses, while improving public order and safety (NL-NGO-4). Another key goal of the LVV was to increase the number of voluntary returns by helping individuals move out of survival mode, regain a sense of control over their lives, and eventually make an informed decision to return to their country of origin (NL-NGO-4, NL-NGO-2). However, the interpretation and implementation of these objectives may vary across cities and organizations, with some putting great emphasis on return, while others on support services. The case of faith-based organizations such as the Pauluskerk in Rotterdam, as examined by Vasileiadi and Swerts (2024), illustrates how the local political environment and the institutional role of these organizations in providing sanctuary to irregular migrants influenced the way the LVV program was implemented.

The goals of the LVV were explored during a focus group held in The Hague as part of the final LVV conference in December 2024. Participants included key stakeholders involved in LVV implementation, such as representatives from municipalities, the central government, and NGOs. The discussion addressed both the explicit and implicit objectives of the LVV identified above.

III. Analysis of outcomes

a. Number of beneficiaries

The scope of the LVV was to give protection to all irregular migrants who were not entitled to any form of national reception. However, beyond this general scope, a range of formal exclusion grounds applied.

Migrants subject to an entry ban, individuals with criminal records, EU citizens, and Dublin claimants were formally excluded from the programme (Mack et al. 2020). In addition, some municipalities also applied other local criteria, such as requiring previous residence in the municipality or excluding people from countries designated as safe countries (Mack et al. 2020). Participation in the LVV also required full cooperation with the program. This included actively working toward a future perspective, whether return or regularization, by for example, contacting personal networks, organizations, or authorities to obtain documentation providing identity and nationality.

Respondents emphasized that in practice, municipalities relaxed the application of the admissibility requirements and sometimes admitted migrants based on their vulnerability, their prospects of regularization or the public nuisance caused if the migrant was left without alternative support options (NL_MUN_1, NL_NGO_1, NL_G_1). In practice, access to the LVV program was not only shaped by formal rules but also by practical and informal obstacles, such as fear of being monitored by authorities or lack of information (NL_NGO_1, NL_NGO_2, NL_NGO_3, NL_NGO_4).

The result was that the LVV program reached only a small portion of the irregular migrants' population in the Netherlands (NL_NGO_1). Until December 2024, approximately 2,980 individuals had been admitted to the program, and around 2,470 had exited because either a sustainable solution was found or because the LVV ended for them⁵ (Ministry of Justice and Security 2025). Of those who exit the program:

- 240 individuals returned to their country of origin or migrated to another country (10%),
- 740 were recognized as asylum seekers after a new application, or were granted a temporary residence permit in the Netherlands due to medical reasons (30%),
- 870 have not received a definitive decision, but a postponement of departure has been granted (i.e. medical reasons) or their asylum application is still pending (35%).
- For the remaining 620 individuals, no solution has been found (25%).

In total, some form of solution, whether through return or regularization, albeit temporary, has been found for around 980 individuals. This accounts for 40% of all those who exited the program. However, it should be noted that some of the solutions are likely to be only semi-durable (Mack et al. 2022): the residence permits are only temporary and can be renewed if the conditions under which were granted persist. This means that temporary legal stays can easily fall back in irregular stay.

When compared to estimates of the irregular migrant population in the Netherlands: over 50,000 in 2018 (Kierans et al. 2024), it becomes clear that the LVV program had a limited reach. However, for those it did support, the impact in terms of human rights was significant. Beyond meeting basic needs, the program provided crucial support to help migrants in making their case for regularization before the Dutch authorities. It is important to highlight that support was offered not only for regularization, but also for return. When individuals did not qualify for regularization, return was actively considered as an alternative. Regularization was therefore one of several pathways explored, not the only focus.

⁵ In certain municipalities such as Rotterdam or Amsterdam, the LVV lasted for 6 or 18 months respectively per person, with possibility of extension in case of demonstrated collaboration from the individual in finding a sustainable solution. The other cities did not have a maximum length of stay (Mack et al. 2020).

b. Cost-benefit analysis

Individual costs and benefits

Through the LVV, irregular migrants benefited from access to shelter, support for accessing healthcare, counselling and assistance with legal paperwork during the time of their enrolment in the LVV. According to the *Koppelingswet* (Linking Act), migrants are excluded from social benefits, with the exception of education (only the age of 18), provision of medically necessary and legal assistance. However, accessing those services is not always easy, as migrants have to deal with bureaucratic difficulties and barriers (Derckx, 2021).

As recognized by migrants participating in the LVV, **shelter** was fundamental as it gave them freedom and safety. Living in other people's houses and being dependent on others made them vulnerable and subject to exploitation (NL_MIG_2). Irregular migrants often depend on their own networks and communities for survival, but these can also become significant sources of abuse (NL_MIG_2, NL_MIG_3). In such cases, shelter programs like the LVV may offer the only means of escape from situations of abuse that occur in private spheres.

Access to **healthcare** can be difficult for irregular migrants. Due to a lack of awareness, Dutch frontline health workers are not always familiar with the rights of irregular migrants, making the role of intermediary organizations crucial in ensuring access to necessary care (NL_NGO_5).

For many migrants, without the support of the LVV, regularization would not have been possible. **Gathering the necessary evidence** to obtain residence permits can be very hard (NL_MUN_1). As one NGO explained, applying for a medical residence permit requires demonstrating that the necessary treatment is unavailable in the country of origin which is hard to prove without assistance from local institutions in the country of origin (NL_NGO_2). This process demands specific expertise about the country of origin, as well as considerable time and resources, that goes well beyond standard legal assistance and support.

Participation in the LVV also comes with costs and trade-offs. One concern is that being in the LVV program places migrants **on the radar of the authorities**, increasing the risk of forced return (NL_MUN_1, NL_NGO_1, NL_NGO_4). Another cost is the **loss of informal networks** and small jobs that migrants rely on to survive.⁶ Entering a shelter sometimes disrupts these fragile support systems.

Societal costs and benefits

The LVV program has contributed to reducing **homelessness** and **improving health outcomes** for irregular migrants (de la Maza & Leerkes 2024, NL_MIG_2, NL_NGO_1, NL_NGO_2). The LVV also helped **encourage returns**, although as mentioned above the return numbers were not high. The LVV moved irregular migrants out of survival mode and allowed them to consider their future realistically, including the possibility of return (NL_NGO_4)

While the shelters bring stability, they may also risk creating a **pull factor** by encouraging undocumented people to remain in the Netherlands, as one interviewee pointed out (NL_NGO_2). The availability of

⁶ On a similar vein, studies have found that shelters are not always suitable for all vulnerable people (Surtees 2008). Some victims of human trafficking for instance, need families around to recover, and the shelter model is not designed in that way.

shelter can make it more difficult for individuals to consider voluntary return. Although this was a politically sensitive outcome, it became an acknowledged reality, as mentioned by one NGO (NL_NGO_2). At the same time, it is hard to prove whether people would have returned if the LVV would have not been in place.

Economic aspects

LVV-related costs varied across municipalities (Ministry of Justice and Security 2024). In 2024, the program cost approximately €33.7 million (Dutch House of Representatives 2024, par. 333). Based on an operational capacity of 1,070 places (Ministry of Justice and Security 2025), this amounts to roughly €31.5 k per place per year. According to DT&V estimates, a forced return operation can cost around €30 k per person, assuming the return can be executed within four months (DT&V n.d.). In contrast, four months of accommodation and support in the LVV costs about €10.5 k per person. While both options are costly, the LVV program appears to be the more economical of the two.

It should also be noted that these figures do not capture the indirect costs that arise when non-return policies in the form of LVV do not exist. If marginalized irregular migrants lack shelter, it can lead to increased emergency health care expenses and costs associated with managing public nuisance (cf. De la Maza Dias & Leerkes 2024).

Political aspects

The LVV brought **governance peace** (*bestuurlijke rust*), as one interviewee explained (NL_G_1). When the LVV was in place, discussions about its implementation remained at the bureaucratic level and were removed from high-level political debates. By taking these discussions out of the political spotlight, bureaucrats were allowed to do their work without interference from national-level politics.

A key strength of the LVV program was the collaboration between institutions, which significantly improved their work. The importance of **inter-agency cooperation**, especially between the IND and NGOs, was repeatedly highlighted by interviewees (NL_G_1, NL_NGO_3).

The LVV also **increased accountability** within state institutions involved in migration governance. The central government took responsibility for the return enforcement gap that occurs when rejected asylum seekers or irregular migrants cannot be returned but also cannot be regularized. Before the establishment of the LVV, municipalities were left alone with the challenges of providing shelter and basic services as well as managing the tensions associated with the presence of irregular migrants in cities (NL_G_1). The LVV also gave organizations, especially the IND (Immigration and Naturalization Service), a feedback opportunity to reassess past asylum decisions, identify possible mistakes, and reconsider whether the criteria used to evaluate such cases needed revision (NL_G_1).

Besides benefits, the LVV also came with political costs. One of the main political tensions surrounding the LVV was its perceived purpose. Rather than being seen as a tool to support return, the LVV was often viewed as **assisting irregular migrants in staying**, especially those who could not be easily returned (NL_G_1).

The LVV also **raised expectations among irregular migrants** about the possibility of **regularization**. Supporting someone through the return process takes time and requires building trust. As one

interviewee explained, from the perspective of return counsellors, the LVV made in some cases the work of return counsellors more difficult (NL_G_1).

Human Rights

The LVV was designed to offer migrants a stable environment to reflect on their lives and consider solutions to their irregular status. By addressing basic needs, such as shelter and healthcare, the program allowed individuals to move beyond survival mode. As one NGO representative noted, this stability provided peace of mind, enabling migrants to make informed decisions about their futures (NL_NGO_1). Many migrants reported that the LVV was the first time during their migration journey that they felt safe (NL_MIG_2, NL_MIG_3). The LVV helped alleviate daily anxieties, allowing them to focus on long-term planning rather than immediate survival.

Beyond meeting basic needs, the LVV aimed to activate migrants' potential by involving them in daily activities and training programs (NL_NGO_3, NL_NGO_4, NL_MIG_2, NL_MIG_3). While these trainings were not tailored to individual needs, they allowed migrants to pursue their interests and rebuild self-confidence (NL_MIG_2).

Despite these efforts, the LVV did not offer formal educational programs. This gap limited migrants' ability to fully develop their capabilities and pursue long-term aspirations. Initial plans to provide access to formal education, such as short-term practical courses, were hindered by a lack of political will (NL_NGO_1). Available trainings were primarily geared toward those preparing for return, focusing on possibilities in their country of origin rather than skill development (NL_NGO_1, NL_NGO_2).

The LVV was instrumental in supporting regularizations by helping migrants collect the necessary evidence, obtain official documentation, and navigate the complexities of Dutch bureaucracy. Aspirations do not end in getting a residence permit, and it is clear that this comes with its own problems (e.g. depression, integration, etc.) (NL_NGO_4, NL_MIG_4), but having papers in the Netherlands, opens up the possibilities for migrants to improve their lives, develop (new) aspirations and depending on the circumstances, realize those aspirations (NL_MIG_2, NL_MIG_3).

Summary

In sum, the LVV program offered a valuable environment where irregular migrants could find stability, safety, and space of mind to think and plan their future. At the individual level, the program helps to mitigate the exclusion that irregular migrants often face in the Netherlands. By giving them access to basic needs, such as shelter and access to health services, they could get out of situations of insecurity and precarity. Socially, it helped reduce homelessness. Although the program had a modest reach, its costs, though considerable, are significantly lower than for forced return policies in the Netherlands, but with a more human-centered approach. Politically, it brought stability, fostered inter-institutional trust and dialogue. However, the program also generated tensions. It sometimes clashed with national return objectives, raised fears of pull factors, and created political discomfort about offering stability to those without the right to stay. Nonetheless, the LVV was a pragmatic and fair approach to address irregular migration in the Netherlands. It created space for institutions to collaborate toward solving the situation of irregularity of many migrants. The program also demonstrated that irregular migration can be addressed not only with return policies, but in combination with regularization policies.

Italy

I. Promising non-return policies in Italy

For the Italian case, the 2020 regularization program (*sanatoria* in Italian) has been analyzed. This program constitutes a specific and *ad hoc* government measure that offers irregular foreign nationals the opportunity to obtain a residence permit and to formalize previously undeclared employment relationships. The measure is framed as an employment-based and sector-specific regularization scheme targeting irregular migrant workers employed in agriculture, domestic work (housekeeping), and personal care and assistance (caregiving).

II. Objectives of the 2020 regularization program in Italy

The 2020 Italian regularization program, introduced under Article 103 of the *Decreto Rilancio*, was framed as a dual response to the COVID-19 emergency and long-standing irregular labor conditions. Its stated objectives were to:

- Guarantee adequate levels of public health protection;
- Legalize existing informal labor in sectors critical to household and food security;
- Ensure continuity of essential services through legal work contracts.

Although public discourse emphasized health and essential services, the program's design reflected pragmatic and selective policy choices. It was restricted to three sectors: domestic work, caregiving, and agriculture. The selected sectors are typically associated with labor shortages and essential services, particularly in private households and food production. Additionally, these sectors are heavily reliant on informal migrant labor, making them prime targets for selective regularization efforts. In line with this, the 2020 Italian regularization programme evinces characteristics associated with non-return policies, particularly in its endeavor to address the long-term presence of irregular migrants who are de facto non-removable due to labour market demand, humanitarian concerns, or administrative barriers to deportation. The emphasis on sectors that are heavily reliant on undeclared labour appears to be a pragmatic acknowledgement of this reality. On the other hand, while the programme explicitly targeted irregular workers, its approach was selective, focusing on specific labour sectors rather than a comprehensive rights-based discourse. In this sense, it could be argued that the issue of non-removability was implicitly addressed by the framing of regularization around economic utility and public health, rather than around migrant rights or legal status per se.

At the same time, their relative invisibility compared to more public-facing sectors (e.g., logistics or construction) made their inclusion less politically contentious. As such, the sectoral focus of the program reflects a pragmatic calculus: address immediate labor needs while minimizing political backlash. Yet, the rationale behind limiting eligibility to only a few sectors appears unfounded, given the substantial presence of migrant workers in other industries such as construction, logistics, manufacturing, and services (Zorzella, 2021). Civil society and advocacy groups supported the measure as a necessary humanitarian and public health response (Perna & Puig Batalla, 2023), particularly in light of migrants' vulnerability during the pandemic.

III. Analysis of outcomes

b. Number of beneficiaries

Unlike previous regularization programs, the 2020 program was also accessible to individuals holding legally precarious residence permits. These included temporary, non-convertible statuses such as asylum

seekers, holders of special or humanitarian protection (especially after the 2018 'Security Decree' reform), as well as those with permits for minor assistance (Art. 31), medical reasons, study, religious motives, or natural disasters. While its primary target were irregular migrants, the program's scope extended beyond classic cases of non-removability to include those in unstable or liminal legal positions, whose risk of falling into irregularity was high. In this sense, the measure functioned not only as a non-return policy but also as a prevention mechanism, aiming to stabilize legal statuses before migrants fell fully outside the system.

The program received over 207,000 applications, with 85% related to domestic and care work, highlighting Italy's dependence on migrant labor in private households (Ministero dell'Interno, 2020). This number surpassed the 2012 program's 134,576 applications. As of June 2023, a total of 132,006 had been approved, 29,181 rejected, and 10,227 withdrawn, while approximately 52% remained under review (ActionAid, 2023). As of 30 June 2024, more than four years after the application window closed, 220,528 applications had been processed, with 153,607 finalized. Out of these, 120,386 permits were issued, reflecting a success rate of around 58%, while 33,239 were officially rejected, indicating a rejection rate of 16% (ActionAid, 2024).

Two types of permits were issued: a work permit tied to an employment contract, and a temporary permit for jobseekers. Both gave access to the national health system (SSN) and were convertible into longer-term residency if conditions were met.

Type of Permit	Access to SSN and Social Services	Convertible into EU Long-Term Residence Permit
Work permit (employment-based)	Upon issuance	After continuous stay and meeting eligibility criteria
Temporary permit for jobseekers	From the provisional phase	Upon employment and conversion

Regionally, Lombardy alone submitted approximately 49,000 applications (24% of the total), followed by Lazio, Campania, Emilia-Romagna, and Sicily. This uneven regional distribution likely reflects both the geography of informal labor and varying administrative capacities across prefectures. However, as of October 2023, nearly 25% of applications remained unresolved. Many applicants entered an "administrative limbo," a legal gray zone marked by prolonged uncertainty (Bonizzoni et al., 2025).

b. Cost-benefit analysis

Individual costs and benefits

This section draws on interviews with nine migrant care workers in Milan (primarily from Peru and El Salvador). They had been living in Italy without legal status for between two and eight years. Furthermore, five employers, including three informal "facilitators" - individuals who informally acted as employers to help migrants regularize their status - have been interviewed. Their accounts reveal the complexities of navigating the system, from successful applications to failure due to employer withdrawal or documentation gaps, as well as shedding light on workaround strategies that emerged to navigate rigid eligibility criteria and reveal the asymmetric power dynamics typical of the care sector. Prior research (van Hooren, 2012; Ambrosini, 2013) has shown how caregiving employment is shaped by intimacy, dependency, informality, and power imbalance, factors that critically affect the negotiation of

rights and legal status. Indeed, critics such as the Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione (ASGI) highlighted the employer-dependent application process, which reinforced paternalistic dynamics and limited migrant agency. Furthermore, eligibility criteria further filtered out potential beneficiaries, including the requirement of uninterrupted presence before 8 March 2020 and a binding employment offer. The program thereby prioritized economic regularization over migrant rights and autonomy. In line with this, Bonizzoni et al. (2021) argue that the program served a signaling function, appeasing EU and civil society pressures while maintaining state control over eligibility. This reflects the logic of "selective inclusion," aimed at short-term political and economic goals rather than structural reform.

Bureaucratic hurdles further complicated the process: applicants had to demonstrate uninterrupted presence in Italy, provide proof of formal residence, and secure housing certificates, often from municipalities applying inconsistent standards. These requirements disproportionately penalized long-term residents living in informal or precarious housing arrangements, an example of a self-perpetuating loop, where the lack of formal housing prevents regularization, while the absence of legal status blocks access to formal housing.

Applicants incurred significant costs: €500 application fees, retroactive social contributions, legal expenses, and, in some cases, fabricated employment arrangements. Although the €500 contribution was formally required to be paid by the employer, in all the interviews conducted, it emerged that the applicants themselves covered the cost. This reflects the de facto burden placed on migrants, despite the legal framework suggesting otherwise, further reinforcing their economic vulnerability and dependency on employer cooperation. One interviewee (Int-2) feigned a babysitting job while actually working in a bar and had to borrow a friend's address for a housing certificate.

Long waiting times became the most frustrating aspect. Very often, a long legal limbo was experienced, with no foreseeable resolution in sight. Despite the growing awareness that no response would be received, repeated phone calls and emails were made to the public authorities in charge in an attempt to obtain information. During this waiting period, only a provisional authorization was granted, preventing expulsion but not permitting enrollment in healthcare or access to social services. In some cases, during the prolonged waiting period, the prospective employer's interest in formalizing the employment relationship was lost, and the application was withdrawn, thereby failing to meet the primary requirement for regularization. This "governance by waiting" (Bonizzoni et al., 2025) technique frustrated applicants and maintained them in a state of dependency and legal precarity.

The emotional toll was also profound. Several interviewees reported long periods of uncertainty, isolation, and psychological distress. Without legal status, many were cut off from healthcare, unable to visit family abroad, and left in a suspended state of being. One migrant (Int-3) described how he could not return to Peru to see his sick relatives for fear of losing his chance at regularization, a situation that exacerbated feelings of helplessness and social marginalization.

When successful, the regularization offered significant benefits. Migrants gained legal visibility, translating into access to health and social services, the ability to rent housing independently, and the possibility of initiating family reunification procedures. Several respondents described the immense psychological relief and restored dignity that came with receiving legal status.

Finally, the 2020 regularization produced both integrative and exclusionary effects. On the one hand, it provided tens of thousands of migrant workers, especially in care and domestic sectors, with recognition,

stability, and visibility. This improved their access to services and rights and contributed to broader social inclusion. According to the data collected, successful cases often resulted in stronger interpersonal ties between employers and workers, greater participation in civic life, and the possibility for long-term planning, such as education or family reunification.

Societal costs and benefits

Economic aspects

From a macroeconomic and public policy standpoint, the 2020 regularization offered economic benefits. According to data published by *Osservatorio Domina*,⁷ the administrative management of the regularization process yielded €30.3 million in net revenue, calculated as the difference between €105.5 million in collected contributions and €75.2 million in administrative costs. Furthermore, with the regularization of 177,000 domestic workers, the program contributed an additional €0.3 billion in revenue from IRPEF (Personal Income Tax) and social security contributions, adding to the €1.5 billion already generated by formally employed domestic workers. Regularization is also expected to help mitigate other economic costs in the long term. By granting migrants access to legal employment and preventive healthcare, it reduces the incidence of untreated illnesses, reliance on emergency services, and exploitative labor conditions that place a burden on public resources. In this way, regularization shifts costs away from expensive, reactive interventions toward more efficient and sustainable forms of care within the public health system. Indeed, a study conducted by the University of Pisa⁸ highlights that regularization facilitates migrants' access to preventive healthcare, thereby reducing late reliance on emergency services and helping to contain public healthcare costs.

Employers also derived social benefits: several reported a sense of dignity and civic fulfillment by formalizing employment relationships and contributing to the welfare state. These dynamics fostered mutual trust and affirmed shared responsibilities, particularly in the context of the pandemic, when care work became even more essential.

Political aspects

From a political perspective, the 2020 regularization programme proved to be a multifaceted instrument, bearing both positive and negative implications. In principle, the measure was presented as both a public health necessity and a pragmatic response to labour shortages in essential sectors during the emergency occasioned by COVID-19. This approach enabled the Italian government to demonstrate its responsiveness to EU institutions, while retaining control over migration flows (Bonizzoni et al., 2021). Policymakers framed the 2020 program as a one-time emergency response to the pandemic, which in turn discouraged further structural reforms. In line with this, the political framing of the programme as a one-off, emergency-driven intervention contributed to institutional inertia. By presenting the regularization as an exception justified by the pandemic, policymakers signaled that such measures are politically acceptable only in times of crisis. As a result, the programme did not pave the way for durable, structural inclusion mechanisms. Rather than offering a replicable model, it reaffirmed Italy's reliance on *ad hoc* and reactive migration governance, limiting the prospects for long-term policy reform.

⁷<https://associazionedomina.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Sanatoria-analisi-Osservatorio-Domina-Comunicato-24.08.2020.pdf>

⁸ https://rtsa.eu/RTSA_2_2020_Carlotti.pdf

The program's design, which was limited to domestic work, caregiving, and agriculture, reflected a political compromise. This compromise was aimed at minimizing visibility and potential backlash while addressing the needs of employers in politically low-profile sectors. However, the process was characterized by significant bureaucratic delays and administrative inefficiencies, which resulted in judicial condemnation of state authorities for systemic inaction (ASGI, 2024). Some employers expressed frustration over unclear procedures and contradictory guidance, revealing a disconnect between national policy and local implementation. In line with this, another case involved a migrant working part-time as an assistant cook and caregiver for an older adult, who was (at the time of the interview) still awaiting the outcome of his application after five years. He only discovered that his application had been archived when he inquired at the immigration office. The primary obstacle was his lack of a passport, having surrendered it when applying for asylum. Although asylum seekers were legally eligible to apply for regularization, his application was blocked by what he described as “an administrative deadlock.” With help from a volunteer lawyer he met through a language course association, he withdrew his asylum claim and submitted his passport to continue the regularization process. Without this support, the application would have remained closed, and he would not have been notified. He also reported being defrauded by someone who charged €1,000 for help with his asylum claim. This experience reflects broader patterns of misinformation and exploitation, which related associations actively try to combat.

Such examples show that individual success in some cases hinges on exceptional social solidarity rather than systemic accessibility. In many cases, churches and associations played a crucial role as intermediaries and advocates. However, the program's reliance on informal support highlights the absence of institutional mechanisms to ensure fair and inclusive access to regularization.

This undermined the credibility of the policy and revealed the state's limited capacity or willingness to implement inclusive migration governance. Moreover, the reliance on employers as gatekeepers reinforced paternalistic dynamics and effectively marginalized migrants' political agency. In conclusion, while the programme furnished the government with symbolic legitimacy and short-term political cover, it did not advance long-term, rights-based migration policy.

Human Rights

From a capabilities perspective, the 2020 regularization offered a formal pathway to legal status and held the potential to enhance migrants' autonomy and well-being. However, it fell short in guaranteeing substantive freedoms for most participants. Drawing on Sen's (1999) and Nussbaum's (2011) capabilities approach, we understand human development not simply as the provision of formal rights, but as the expansion of real opportunities. In this context, the program's structure imposed substantial limitations on what Sen refers to as “substantive freedoms,” the genuine ability of individuals to act on behalf of goals they have reason to value. For Sen, this extends beyond formal legal rights, encompassing the enabling conditions that allow individuals to make meaningful choices. In the absence of such conditions, rights remain nominal rather than real.

A participant captured this gap when she explained: *“I had the right to regularize myself but was at the hand of him [the employer] who did not help me.”* Her employer failed to support the application process and, as she recounted, *“did not present at the office properly”* and *“did not submit anything.”* Despite having a legal entitlement, her access to regularization was effectively blocked by another's inaction. This illustrates how, without autonomy from third-party gatekeepers, formal rights do not translate into actual capabilities, echoing Sen's emphasis on the distinction between entitlements and freedoms.

The program's employer-dependent design meant that irregular migrants could not submit applications independently, placing the entire process in the hands of their employers. This severely curtailed what Nussbaum (2011) calls the capability for "practical reason", the capacity to critically assess and pursue one's goals and aspirations. This capability is undermined when individuals cannot direct their own legal or life trajectories but must rely on others to access basic rights, including legal status.

One employer (Int-10) recounted how she was asked to help a migrant worker whose original employers, despite being well-off, refused to complete the procedure. *"They told her, 'If you want, we'll pay you more, but we can't follow you through this procedure,'" she explained. The woman had been working for a family that split their time between Italy and France and had little interest in dealing with Italian bureaucracy. "They went to the office once, saw the line, and left her there." Although the interviewee did not need to hire anyone, she decided to help: "I had neither the intention nor the need to hire someone, but I'm glad I did."* She offered a contract and submitted the application, relying on support from a volunteer lawyer: *"He told me what to say and do, we were guided through everything."*

This case illustrates how employer support could go far beyond paperwork, and how the roles of volunteer and employer often overlapped in practice. In this instance, the employer offered a contract out of solidarity rather than labor need, reflecting a broader informal practice sometimes described as *"fictitious employment"* for humanitarian purposes. The employer also encouraged the worker's educational goals and accompanied her to university open days. *"She wants to study, and I tell her she must; she is talented."* At the same time, she expressed frustration with structural inequality: *"It is such a shame that she cannot just come here with her passport, like French or British young people do."* These dynamics echo Ambrosini (2013) and Marchetti (2013), who describe how such arrangements form part of an "invisible" or informal welfare system, especially where irregular status limits access to formal rights and protections, particularly for domestic workers.

Furthermore, the program's narrow sectoral scope limited the types of work that qualified for regularization, excluding many migrants employed in other sectors. By confining eligibility to domestic work, caregiving, and agriculture, the state implicitly determined which labor forms merited recognition and protection. This not only constrained migrants' economic opportunities but also shaped what they could realistically aspire to.

Summary

In conclusion, the 2020 Italian regularization showed only limited potential as a durable non-return policy. Politically, presenting the measure as a temporary and exceptional response to the pandemic made it feasible in the short term but hindered any move toward lasting structural reform. Although it formally extended rights, its relatively narrow reach – numbers are still considerably larger than for non-return policies examined in the other focal countries – and dependence on employer cooperation severely restricted its ability to support migrants' real freedoms. While the program contributed to increased tax and social security payments from regularized workers, its fragmented implementation limited broader and more lasting benefits for the host society.

Poland

I. Promising non-return policies in Poland

There were three regularization programs carried out in Poland in the past: in 2003, 2007 and 2012. Since 2014, there are provisions grounded in the Law on Foreigners of 2013⁹ allowing for **individual regularization in very specific cases**. The migration strategy entitled 'Regaining Control, Ensuring Security'¹⁰ announced in October 2024, emphasizes improving the return policy, preventing irregular border crossings and irregular entry to Polish territory, rather than developing non-return accommodation policies. Based on the available information and data collected in the FAiR study, the following paragraphs discuss the selected individual **regularization mechanisms** in detail, their costs and benefits, as well as ideas of expanding or improving them. The analysis focuses on the permission to stay for **humanitarian reasons** and **conventions-related permits**.

Two authorities issue permits allowing for a lawful stay to migrants in an irregular situation in Poland: 1) the Border Guard and 2) provincial offices (*voivodeship*). Permissions issued by the Border Guard are available to irregular migrants who are detected by the authorities and meet the criteria for initiating a return procedure¹¹, but who do not meet the criteria for the execution of a return order. In Poland, this is the Border Guard that is responsible not only for border control but also for legality checks in the entire territory of Poland. The authority is also responsible for issuing and executing return orders. In the course of the return procedure, the Border Guard must investigate whether the person meets the criteria for being permitted to stay for humanitarian reasons or to receive a toleration permit. The two types of permission issued by the Border Guard encompass:

1. A permission to stay for **humanitarian reasons** (hereinafter: permission for humanitarian stay) – issued when obligation to return 1) can only be enforced to a country where a migrant's right to life, liberty and personal safety would be threatened, or where a migrant would be subjected to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, forced to work, or deprived of the right to a fair trial or be punished without legal basis, or 2) would violate migrant's right to family life or private life, or 3) would violate the rights of the child and seriously impair his or her physical or mental development (Article 348); it may be granted to people who were refused international protection;
2. A permission for tolerated stay – issued when permission for humanitarian stay is not possible due to legal obstacles (e.g. serious crime, threat to public safety), when return is impossible for reasons beyond anyone's control, or when return is legally prohibited (Article 351).

These permissions are issued for an indefinite period, although migrants need to renew their cards confirming these permissions every two years. However, these permissions may be revoked, if the reasons for not issuing a return order are no longer valid. The permissions may also be withdrawn if their holders leave Poland or return to their countries of origin. Both types of permission issued by the Border

⁹ Ustawa z dnia 12 grudnia 2013 r. o cudzoziemcach (t.j. Dz. U. z 2024 r. poz. 769 z późn. zm.).

¹⁰ Kancelaria Prezesa Rady Ministrów (2024). "Odzyskać kontrolę. Zapewnić bezpieczeństwo" - strategia migracyjna na lata 2025 - 2030.

¹¹ See Article 302 of the Law on Foreigners of 2013 (Ustawa z dnia 12 grudnia 2013 r. o cudzoziemcach (t.j. Dz. U. z 2024 r. poz. 769 z późn. zm.) specifies the situations when the return order is issued. Among them, there are: lack of valid documents authorising a migrant to stay in Poland, performing work despite having no authorisation to do so, purpose of stay not in accordance with the declaration, not leaving the territory of Poland despite obligation to do so within 30 days of being issued a final negative decision on asylum application.

Guard¹² authorize migrants to stay on the territory of Poland, access the labour market, apply for a permanent residence permit (after 10 years in case of migrants with a permission for tolerated stay, and 5 years in case of holders of permission for humanitarian stay). Crossing the border (in any direction) is not allowed based on the permission for tolerated stay, while holders of a permission for humanitarian stay are allowed to do so. They may obtain a temporary Polish travel document, in case their travel documents are no longer valid, have been lost and obtaining them from the country of citizenship is not possible. Holders of permission for tolerated stay do not have this opportunity. In addition, they may be subjected to additional control measures, such as an obligation to report to the authorities. **Permission for humanitarian stay** or for tolerated stay are considered a form of protection from return. However, as the empirical study proved, the permission to stay for humanitarian reasons is also considered a **promising non-return policy**.

In specific circumstances irregular migrants may also obtain short-term or temporary residence permits issued by the provincial offices in the first instance, or by the Office for Foreigners in the second instance. They include explicit regularization mechanisms (hereinafter: **conventions-related permits**), i.e. temporary residence permits issued for up to three years in a very specific cases, applicable when 1) a foreigner's stay in Poland is necessary due to the need to respect the right to family life within the meaning of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Article 187(6)); or when 2) a foreigner's departure from Poland would violate the rights of the child as defined in the Convention on the Rights of the Child, to an extent that would seriously threaten his or her mental and physical development (Article 187(7)). In the study, this type of temporary residence permit has been also considered a possible alternative to return, provided that the existing law is applied properly in practice. Other laws allowing for short-term (Article 181) or temporary legalization of stay (as in the case of officially identified victims of trafficking in human beings, based on Articles 176, or exploited migrant workers with official victim status in the criminal proceedings, based on Articles 187(4) and 187(5)) were not discussed in detail in the study, although they were also mentioned as implicit or explicit policies allowing for regularization.

It is sometimes debatable whether the conventions-related residence permits, together with the permission for humanitarian stay, can always be seen as non-return accommodation policies: it could also be argued that Poland does (only) issue such permits in response to challenges in enforcing return since Poland may in some cases be required under international and European law to provide residence permits in the circumstances mentioned. However, the provisions on 'conventions-related' permits (Article 187(6-7)) are worded in such a way that these permits *may*, but do not have to, be granted, which suggests that the authorities also have the option to issue negative decisions that will eventually lead to return decisions. If the authorities see the possibility of securing the right to family life, protection of the rights of the child and respect for private life *in the country of origin*, then return is indeed prioritized, as a justified consequence of violating immigration law.

II. Objectives of non-return policies in Poland

In case of permission for a humanitarian stay (Article 348), positive decisions should be issued if the prerequisites, i.e. humanitarian reasons, are found (PL-RT ex 9). Despite doubts expressed by some study participants (e.g., PL-RT ex 3, PL-EX-2) about the law application in practice, the representatives of

¹² The only one exception when the permission for tolerated stay is issued upon application is when a migrant is supposed to return to a country to which s/he must not be returned according to a court's verdict or a decision of the Minister of Justice on a refusal of extradition (Article 356(4) and 351(3) of the Law on Foreigners).

authorities (PL-RT ex 6, ex 7) assure that in the course of the return procedure border guards ask questions that allow to properly assess the situation of a migrant and to legalize the stay of people who – “according to the Polish axiology reflected in the already existing law” (PL-RT ex 6) – deserve it. The objective of issuing the permission for humanitarian stay refers to prevention of violation of fundamental rights (such as human dignity, right to freedom, respect for family life; see also above).

This mentioned axiology assumes that unsuccessful legalization and violations of the conditions of stay should end with a return and only in exceptional cases migrants should be given a possibility to stay legally in Poland (PL-RT ex 6). Such objectives are also reflected in the conventions-related permits that serve first of all to protect the right to family life and the rights of the child. The best interest of the child seems the most important value to be protected while allowing either the child, or their parents to stay on the territory of Poland.

III. Analysis of outcomes

a. Number of beneficiaries

The number of permissions for humanitarian stay issued every year does not exceed 300, and for tolerated stay – 40 (between 2022-2025). Such numbers are considered very low in the context of the relatively large number of immigrants in Poland. At the end of 2024, holders of permits for humanitarian stay constituted less than 0.1 per cent of the population of foreigners with valid residence cards (amounting to almost 2 million, not covering visa holders and migrants staying within the visa-free regime) (Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców, n.d.). Publicly available statistics do not provide information on how many residence permits were issued based on conventions-related regularization mechanisms. Regarding permits issued to victims of trafficking, in 2023, there were 46 such permits issued (MSWiA, Departament Porządku Publicznego 2024).

The total number of foreigners who have been granted residence permits under the three regularization programs, mentioned at the beginning of the Polish case study, carried out in Poland in the past (in 2003, 2007 and 2012) has reached around 7,000 (out of around 15,000 who applied for this opportunity) (see more in Fagasiński, Górczyńska, and Szczepanik 2015).

b. Cost-benefit analysis

Individual costs and benefits

As migrants declared, and which was echoed by the representatives of civil society organizations, even if there are provisions allowing regularization, taking advantage of them is very difficult due to their complexity and costs of professional legal services. But the most important reason is fear of being detected and eventually returned, instead of being granted legal status, as taking advantage of any of those procedures entails reporting themselves to border guards. The uncertainty of the results of a regularization attempt has been commented by a lawyer in the following way: “*lawyers who support irregular migrant cannot guarantee that it will end well, so we are, so to speak, torn between certain possibilities that exist in the regulations, this uncertainty, and this very risky move of revealing themselves and hoping that everything will end positively*” (PL-RT ex 9).

The uncertainty about the effect stems from the administrative discretion and complexity of cases processed under regularization-related provisions. A representative of the public administration (PL-RT ex 6) admitted that the permissions or permits based on respect for private life and social ties are often

issued in the second instance, as in the first instance the situation of migrants was not investigated properly or there were procedural errors. Such practice leads to additional emotional and also financial costs on the side of migrants.

Regularization brings emotional benefits as it eliminates, or at least reduces, the fear of deportation and the fear that irregular status may expose migrants to unfair treatment, exploitation or intimidation (e.g., PL-M-1, PL-RT ex 1, ex 3). All in all, migrants appreciate the freedom and relative comfort that regular status gives them, as *“being invisible is not that easy”* (PL-M-1). Migrants granted permissions for humanitarian stay or conventions-related permits appreciate in particular the possibility to cross the border, to visit families in the countries of origin, and to attend important celebrations. Having authorization to stay, migrants may plan their future and start benefitting from regular status: have regular work (which may require a work permit or another document authorizing access to the labour market in Poland), access to public health insurance and thus access to healthcare in Poland. If they work lawfully and contribute to the social insurance system, they may have access to special benefits and the right to pension when they retire (PL-M-1, PL-M-7). An expert supporting employers in legalization procedures emphasized that regularization significantly strengthens migrant’s position in the labour market and facilitates integration (PL-EX-4).

Regarding access to regularization, special attention should be paid to migrants affected by unfair practices of others (employers, labour recruiters, immigration service providers), migrants without children or (formal) partners in Poland, not being identified formally as victims of trafficking or labour exploitation. In general, they do not meet criteria for the existing regularization mechanisms. Either they try to survive as irregular migrants (which is possible but may bring risks related to exploitation), or they have to consider leaving Poland, as it may be the only way to go back on a legal path.

Migrants deprived of access to regularization mechanisms may look for other solutions to legalize their stay, not necessarily compliant with the law or not necessarily reflecting the actual stay in Poland, such as looking for a Polish spouse just to legalize their stay. A few experts (e.g., PL-RT ex 5, ex 8, ex 1, PL-EX-5) noticed that such solutions bring only short-term benefits on an individual level, if migrants are eventually granted legal status, based for instance on having a Polish spouse. However, if the marriage is found by the administration as a way to circumvent the law, the consequences for migrants and also Polish spouses may be serious, including criminal charges and punishment (see e.g. Szulecka & Klaus 2021). Therefore, looking for solutions that in fact circumvent the law means costs in many dimensions: financial, emotional, constant fear that the abuse may be revealed and end up with criminal or administrative sanctions, including deportation.

Societal costs and benefits

Economic aspects

As one of the migrant interviewees stated *“it does not work for the benefit of the Polish society that we are kept in an irregular status. This is a matter of fact that one way or another we are here, and we will not evaporate. That I will not evaporate as snow in spring. I will stay and will be a burden for the state system”* (PL-M-1). In addition, irregular migrants contribute to the informal economy. This has been confirmed by this study, also by migrants themselves (PL-M-1, PL-M-6, PL-M-7). Although work in the informal economy can be safe and satisfactory in economic terms (PL-M-1), there is always a risk that irregular migrants are exposed to frauds, exploitation (PL-M-7) and threats (PL-M-6). But irregular migrant workers may also act to the detriment of employers for which they cannot be held liable, because the employer would have to report himself (PL-M-1).

To have social and economic profits from regularization mechanisms that also facilitate access to the labour market, a migrant needs authorization to work in Poland (which is the case when conventions-related permits are granted), an employer must be interested in lawful employment and follow the rules in practice. If this is not the case, the risk of irregularization increases. In turn, social costs also increase if the population of irregular migrants is growing. From the perspective of the economy and the society, keeping migrants in an irregular situation, allowing someone (employers, local economies) to benefit from their work and at the same time not offering migrants a way to lawful employment may be seen as unfair (PL-EX-2, PL-EX-4). However, one of the experts (PL-EX-5) emphasized that offering regularization to irregular migrant workers, who consciously agreed to stay in the informal economy for their own benefits, could be also seen as unfair, especially by all migrants who follow the rules, even if this means lower net salary.

However, as one study participant claimed, in the light of the repeated calls for facilitating recruitment of migrant workers from third countries, it seems more profitable to offer regularization to those who are already present in Poland for work-related purposes: *“why make people leave Poland, if they are already working, and then suddenly bring other foreigners to Poland because there is a shortage of labour”* (PL-RT ex 1). Offering irregular migrants working in Poland a way to regularization brings profits, *“because these people are actually working, but due to their illegal status, they cannot pay contributions or taxes”* (PL-EX-2). Migrants kept in the informal economy are also unused potential that *“can be considered a loss for the economy”* (PL-EX-4). People pushed to the informal economy may also contribute to criminality, being both victims or offenders, or be exposed to extreme poverty. These are serious social problems that require public intervention and incur costs. Therefore, effective regularization mechanisms and accessible information about them and about the rules may also bring profits to the society as a whole, through preventing crime, marginalization and degradation of migrants (PL-EX-4).

Political aspects

Since the mid-2010s, Poland's approach to irregular migration has been to either prevent their arrival or silently allowing onward migration to neighboring EU Member States (a policy that could be named ‘double externalization’) and, if possible, return them to their countries of origin. While individual regularization is possible, lawyers view the criteria as too narrow—especially given past ease of labour market access, weak oversight of intermediaries, and barriers to long-term residence. This is why some experts (see also Klaus et al. 2024, 41) propose expanding the criteria for temporary residence permits for irregular migrants – especially those affected by others’ misconduct (e.g. employers, intermediaries) or delays at provincial offices. However, these ideas are questioned by public authorities and some lawyers. There is no support for a broader regularization program, which experts see as unrealistic and potentially harmful, citing risks like ‘abolition tourism’ and pull factors (e.g., PL-RT ex 1, ex 6, ex 8, ex 7). In the study, experts also mentioned the consequences of communicating that violating the law may be ignored or forgotten. Therefore, it is crucial to put efforts to communicate with migrants and all other actors involved in migratory processes that the law should be respected in every phase, from the very beginning of migratory processes. In this context, an immigration lawyer emphasized: *“If we assume that we are a democratic state governed by the rule of law, we cannot show that there is a category of people living in this state who are not subject to the law”* (PL-EX-5).

A representative of a civil society organization supporting migrants emphasized that migrants regularized in individualized procedures may be more prone to respect Polish law, and *“such people are then better citizens of Poland if they are more aware of their rights and even go through such a process, they will not allow themselves to be cheated again and will simply function better if they care”* (PL-EX-3). To allow the society to benefit from regularization mechanisms, there should be clear information that people who do not care, ignore the rules, and abuse the available options for migration (e.g. overstay the periods allowed in the visa-free regime) will face the administrative consequences, i.e. return to the country or origin. Therefore, effective return policy, communicated to the public, may in fact increase the societal benefits from regularization mechanisms as it will be a message that the opportunity for regularization is given in exceptional cases and to people who are interested in legalization, who care about their legal status (e.g., PL-RT ex 1, ex 8, ex 3).

Therefore, only individual regularization, in very specific circumstances, is seen by the authorities and some experts representing other groups as a beneficiary option, reducing the risk of pull effects. If humanitarian reasons for stay are respected and conventions-related regularization mechanisms are efficient, there are almost no political costs, even in the era of migration policy becoming more and more restrictive. This is because the prerequisites for regularization refer to values, such as respect for family life and children’s rights, that seem to be shared by the majority of the society. In a recent study on a desirable migration policy, humanitarianism and human rights have been indicated as the second most important values (by 56.4% of survey participants, i.e. institutional actors) on which migration policy in Poland should be built (Jaroszewicz et al. 2024, 23). Security was indicated as the first one, though.

Regarding administrative costs, the regularization mechanisms cannot be discussed without the wider context. For several years now, high workload at provincial offices, inefficient procedures, as well as frequent and significant rotation of personnel have been observed. An introduction of new provisions or new policies to be dealt with in these offices would be an additional burden, and thus bring some administrative cost (e.g., PL-EX-2). The resources of the offices should be increased and spent on improving the procedures in general, including the regularization procedures that are not easy and are based on administrative discretion, which *“creates room for abuse, widespread corruption”*¹³ (PL-EX-3). To prevent this, regularization procedures need to be transparent and properly administered. Only this may contribute to the increase of migrants’ trust in public institutions.

Indeed, the only cost of conventions-related permits, found in the study, relates to the burden of processing the applications. Most of the study participants who are familiar with legalization procedures at provincial offices see administrative discretion and complicated cases of migrants waiting for regularization as a huge challenge (e.g., PL-EX-5). Such cases require knowledge and experience, which may be lacking in the overwhelmed provincial offices, suffering from rotation of personnel and huge caseload. In that sense, the existence of a regularization mechanism based on protecting rights to family life or the rights of the child means cost on the side of administration. However, considering the relatively narrow reach of this policy, the costs are limited, and certainly much lower than in the case of regularization programs executed in the past (PL_RT ex 1, ex 8, ex 6).

¹³ There was a number of criminal cases initiated in relation to the accusations of bribery of employees of the voivodship offices involved in administrative procedures of legalizing stay of migrants. See e.g., Prokuratura Okręgowa w Gdańsku (2024). Zatrzymania w śledztwie prowadzonym w sprawie korupcji w Pomorskim Urzędzie Wojewódzkim w Gdańsku.

On the other hand, the narrow reach may mean that people who are afraid of returning or are unwilling to return seek ways to legalize their status, even though they do not meet the requirements under the applicable regulations. For the administration, this means higher costs associated with verifying the authenticity of documents and the credibility of arguments (such as marriage to a Polish citizen). If abuse or fraud is detected, further procedures are initiated, which can be costly and time-consuming. Such costs, as some experts claimed (e.g., PL_RT ex 5), directly stem from the lack of pathways for regularization in other cases than human trafficking, labour exploitation or humanitarian grounds.

Human Rights

Polish provisions allowing for case-by-case regularization refer mostly to human rights such as the right to life, freedom from torture or inhumane and degrading treatment, right to family life, prevention of forced labour and right to freedom, and rights of the child. The practice raises more questions as the private life of migrants, especially being in informal relationships, is sometimes not considered when making decisions on issuance of conventions-related temporary residence permits or permissions for humanitarian stay (PL-RT ex 4). The often-mentioned inefficiency and excessive workload of provincial offices in Poland causes that sometimes people are 'stuck' in the procedures which may be seen as violation of the right to good administration that affects the lives of individuals. As one expert commented on this, *"someone is terminally ill and there is no instrument to speed up the processing of the application"* (PL_ex_4).

Last but not least, rights of crime victims or of people affected by exploitative practices should be mentioned. A lawyer supporting migrant victims of labour exploitation rightly pointed out to the significance of legal status in accessing victim's rights: *"I believe that it is extremely beneficial when they have legalized residence in Poland and know perfectly well that they will not be obliged to return. And then they can take action against their current or former employers"* (PL_ex_2).

Summary

In the beginning of the first decade of the 21st century, irregular migrants were recognized as a population deserving state's attention with the aim of including them in the society as taxpayers, lawful residents, and declared migrant workers. Such an approach is rather uncommon in the public discourse of 2025. Whereas irregular migration is recognized as a problem, the solution searched for include rather exclusionary policies such as preventing irregular arrival, refusal of entry, and returns, both voluntary and forced. According to the declared migration policy, a chance to regularize the stay should be given only in very exceptional cases to people whose stay in Poland is justified by the need to protect right to family life or children's rights or very specific life circumstances, such as serious health problems, being affected by labour exploitation or human trafficking. And there are provisions offering ways to regularize based on these circumstances. However, their application requires improvement to bring benefits to individuals, the society, and the economy, with respect for human rights and for the main rules that Poland's migration policy is based on, i.e. focusing on legal migration and prevention of irregular migrants' presence in Poland.

To sum up, in Poland, there are provisions allowing irregular migrants to get permissions for humanitarian stay or to apply for temporary residence permits that can be a pathway to long-term regular stay, without the necessity to leave Poland. They are explicit, embedded in the legislation procedure and individualized, which is expected to reduce possible pull effects. On paper, these solutions can be treated as a promising non-return policy; however, existing provisions are currently hardly accessible, untransparent and unpredictable, turning them into a very narrow niche opening for only a few individuals.

Switzerland

I. Promising non-return policies in Switzerland

The Swiss Foreign Nationals and Integration Act (FNIA) and the Swiss Asylum Act (AsyIA) define specific circumstances of personal hardship under which individuals may be granted a residence permit, even if they would not otherwise qualify (known as the *Härtefallregelung* or hardship provision). Some of these circumstances can be seen as creating a ground for non-return accommodation policies, particularly when they target individuals who have received a return order following an asylum procedure. However, this regularization mechanism also extends to individuals who are still awaiting a decision on their asylum application, as well as to those without legal residence status outside the asylum system—for instance, individuals who have remained in Switzerland after the expiration of a residence or work permit. As most people who grant a residence permit based on the *Härtefallregelung* are people with a temporary protection status, this instrument is not an explicit policy for non-return but one that also opens legal pathways for those who previously received a return decision.

The current regulation is based on a partial revision of the AsyIA taking place in 2007. It provides Swiss cantons the main responsibility in this matter, differentiates between three different constellations that can entitle for the *Härtefallregelung* (see SEM 2025a, 2025b):

1. In cases of severe personal hardship for foreigners (art. 30 para. 1B FNIA) – this option is especially important for sans-papiers.
2. In cases of persons who have granted temporary protection and lived at least 5 years in Switzerland (art. 84 para. 5 FNIA).
3. In cases of hardship for persons with pending asylum decision (art. 14 para. 2 AsyIA) – who have lived at least 5 years in Switzerland and are considered to be well integrated.

In all three cases, a Swiss B permit (valid for five years) is granted. In principle, the permit B can be renewed multiple times for 5 more years if the legal requirements are met (SEM 2022). However, in the case of unemployment, the cantons may extend the permit only for one more year if the person has been unemployed for more than 12 months.

The procedure for regularization in all three legal fields requires acceptance of two administrative levels. First, the Swiss cantons act as gatekeepers and check whether the conditions are met and if the person is considered to be entitled to a cantonal residence permit. If this is the case, the application is submitted to the Swiss State Secretariat for Migration (SEM), which ultimately has the final decision-making power. In most cases, however, the SEM follows the recommendations of the cantonal authorities providing them with the main responsibility in this matter (Wichmann et al. 2011).

If the canton does not approve the application, it is not forwarded to the SEM and there is no possibility of appeal. In such cases, the application is rejected without reaching the federal level. In light of the substantial variation in the practice between the cantons, critics have described the process of regularization as a ‘lottery’—from the outset of the current regulation (e.g., Der Bund 2009) up to the present day (e.g., Beobachter 2024).

In 2013, a motion was introduced in Parliament to facilitate the regularization of young people aged 14–17 in the field of vocational training (Motion Barthassat). A simplified procedure was supposed to allow

young sans-papiers to be regularized in order to complete an apprenticeship. However, due to the low number of regularizations carried out, the motion is considered to have had only symbolic importance. Research suggests that affected individuals do not take up the procedure because of fears that their families could be deported in the event of a rejection (Wichmann et al. 2011; Morlok et al. 2015).

A recent case of a more coordinated cantonal approach to regularization, within the federal framework, is the Geneva *Operation Papyrus* that was implemented between 2017 and 2018 (Consoli 2024). It was based on a jointly agreed set of transparent criteria between the canton of Geneva and the SEM, aiming to regularize sans-papiers working and living in Geneva in stable conditions. Nevertheless, even in this case the competence remained formally at the federal level, and Geneva used its discretionary power to extend residence permits within the scope of existing law, defining and applying eligibility criteria coherently (Morlok et al. 2015).

II. Objectives of the *Härtefallregelung* in Switzerland

The objectives of the 2007 partial revision of the AsylG, during which the current *Härtefallregelung* was introduced, were the prevention of hardship, the improvement of the status of temporarily admitted persons, and better integration into the labour market (Bundesamt für Migration 2006; The Federal Council 2007). The outcome of the regularization procedure based on the *Härtefallregelung* is distinguished from the outcome of the asylum procedure. Consequently, the regularization procedures do not serve the purpose of preventing personal persecution or situations of general violence or war in the applicant's country of origin.

The objectives of the *Härtefallregelung* have been predominantly focused on the individual situation and the prevention of personal hardship. At least officially, there are hardly any broader economic or societal justifications for the system beyond the aim of preventing personal hardship on a case-by-case basis.

III. Analysis of outcomes

a. Number of beneficiaries

There are no official and systematic statistics on how many regularization applications are submitted and rejected in all cantons. The SEM statistics only report on cases that are actually submitted by the cantons, i.e. only cases that the cantons have approved.

For 2024, the SEM (2025a) has communicated the following figures for the three constellations that potentially entitle for regularization via the *Härtefallregelung*:

- art. 30 FNIA: 903 cases approved upon cantonal propositions, 5 rejections
- art. 84 FNIA: 4,279 cases approved upon cantonal propositions, 18 rejections,
- art. 14 AsyIA: 319 cases approved upon cantonal propositions, 32 rejections.

The numbers show that the vast majority of the people benefiting from the *Härtefallregelung* have already been granted a protection status and lived for more than five years in Switzerland. These numbers must be seen in relation to the, at a European level, comparably slightly above average numbers of asylum applications in Switzerland (above 27,000 cases in 2024) as well as the estimate of the numbers of sans-papiers in the country. According to Morlok et al. (2015), the best estimate for the number of sans-papiers in Switzerland is at around 76,000 persons (range: 50,000–99,000). Earlier estimates were

substantially higher and predominantly assigned the number to the Swiss labour market, not the asylum system (Longchamp et al. 2005).

Differences in the application of the *Härtefallregelung* between cantons are particularly pronounced along linguistic lines. In particular, French-speaking cantons such as Geneva and Vaud appear more willing to make use of the hardship provision. Researchers attribute this to greater political openness and the stronger influence of civil society actors in these regions (Achermann & Efiouyi-Mäder 2003).

b. Cost-benefit analysis

To date, there have been few systematic evaluations regarding macro effects of the regularization mechanism in Switzerland. Nor are there representative surveys on the experiences of those affected or on their integration trajectories. Nevertheless, some studies offer insights into the broader economic and political context and effects of regularization, and the ways in which the mechanism shapes individuals' personal situations.

Individual costs and benefits

There is limited research on individual costs and benefits of the *Härtefallregelung*. From an individual perspective, the regularization through this mechanism represents a shift from a temporary and uncertain situation to a more permanent situation, including a broader set of rights. It allows for projecting a personal and professional future in Switzerland, freeing them from the potential enforcement of a return decision or the termination of a temporary protection status. This is particularly important as the temporary status often implies restrictions on a professional career and family reunification. From an economic perspective, regularization appears to ensure financial stability but only rarely leads to significant upward mobility (Morlok et al. 2015).

Research on the individual experiences of those regularized under Operation Papyrus indicates that the extent of the psychological stress caused by the absence of legal residence only became apparent after the process of regularization. This suggests a *de-vulnerabilization effect* of this regularization scheme: a psychological shift linked to the end of deportability and criminalization (Concoli, 2024). However, while regularization is associated with better mental health and life satisfaction, the administrative process of regularization is often associated with high levels of stress and anxiety (Cullati et al., 2025).

Societal costs and benefits

Economic aspects

To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies systematically evaluating the broader macroeconomic consequences of the *Härtefallregelung* in Switzerland. However, studies assessing the situation of those regularized suggest that the regularization can generally be considered successful from an economic perspective (see Morlok et al. 2015). According to data from the SEM, around 80% of persons regularized under art. 14 AsylA and over 90% under Art. 30 FNIA are in employment six months after acceptance. Yet while these outcomes may reflect the economic advantages of the Swiss regularization mechanism, they also partly result from the high eligibility requirements associated with the *Härtefallregelung* as being financially self-sufficient often is one of the criteria for benefiting from this regularization scheme.

Political aspects

The history of the Swiss regularization mechanism shows that it is embedded in a contentious political discourse. Notably, the current form of the *Härtefallregelung* was introduced in 2007 as part of a broader reform of the Asylum Act, led by Christoph Blocher, then Minister of the Justice and Police Department and former leader and chief strategist of the Swiss People's Party, known for its anti-immigration stance. During the legislative process, most criticism came from the political left. For example, the Social Democrat Vermot-Mangold described it as an overly cautious regulation ('*zaghafte Harte Fallregelung*') within an overall 'bleak' asylum reform (The Swiss Parliament 2006). Simonetta Sommaruga, then also a member of parliament for the Social Democrats and later herself Minister of the Justice and Police Department, criticized the fact that decisions under the *Härtefallregelung* could vary between cantons (*ibid.*). These two points arguably still reflect the main concerns raised in political debates today. The Swiss Refugee Council, for instance, has criticized the regulation from the outset, claiming that the implementation of the regularization mechanism is overly strict and inconsistent.

The political right, by contrast, has criticized initiatives such as Operation Papyrus as overly permissive and as sending the wrong signal. In response, they have proposed measures such as the 2017 parliamentary initiative *Illegality is not a personal hardship* (*Die Illegalität ist kein Härtefall*, parliamentary initiative 17.414), arguing that Operation Papyrus encourages the arrival of unqualified workers from third countries (Swiss Parliament 2017). Regardless, the political debate surrounding the regularization mechanism has at least contributed to raising awareness of the existence and challenges faced by *sans-papiers*. However, some observers argue that the debate has also tended to trivialize the issue—caught between expressions of solidarity on the one hand and calls for deterrence-oriented policies on the other (Efionayi-Mäder et al. 2010).

Human rights

The Swiss regularization mechanism provides beneficiaries of this scheme with a broad set of individual rights. Most importantly, it allows them to change from an illegalized situation or one with a temporary permit to a more durable solution. However, while the set of rights can generally be perceived as broad, the reach has generally been narrow as only a comparably small number of people have benefited from the Swiss regularization mechanism. Moreover, the *Härtefallregelung* reflects an implicit mechanism and alternative to situations of non-return. In fact, most people benefiting from this regularization mechanism never received a return decision but have been granted temporary protection status.

Summary

The Swiss pathway could be regarded as a promising model to replicate, given that it has been successfully implemented in a context of restrictive asylum reform, provides beneficiaries with a broad set of rights, and appears to contribute to economic stability. However, the manner in which it is implemented—typically very restrictive, varying between cantons, and available only to those who have resided in Switzerland for at least five years (and, in practice, often considerably longer)—significantly limits its potential as a viable solution to the challenge of limited return.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This comparative study examined prominent non-return policies in Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, Poland, and Switzerland, focusing particularly on those that appear promising – that is, policies that seem (1) respectful to human rights and capable of promoting human development, are (2) potentially

beneficial for host societies and, relatedly, (3) politically feasible. The analyzed policies include Germany's *Ausbildungsduldung* and other labor- and integration-based regularization mechanisms, the Netherlands' *Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening* (LVV), Italy's sector-based regularization programs, Poland's permission for humanitarian stay and conventions-related temporary residence permits, and Switzerland's *Härtefallregelung*. To varying degrees, these policies seek to address the situation of irregular migrants whose return is difficult or impossible to enforce¹⁴. The specific characteristics of these policies nonetheless vary when it comes to the level of social and economic rights granted, their reach (i.e., how many migrants are targeted and have access), and their explicitness and structural anchoring in existing legal frameworks. All non-return policies assessed seek to reconcile competing pressures of immigration control, human rights, and economic pragmatism.

Country	Key findings
<i>Germany</i>	The two explicit regularization pathways appear relatively promising: they yield societal and economic benefits, respect human rights, and enable individual capabilities, supported by public acceptance due to their labour- and integration-oriented focus. However, high eligibility criteria, bureaucratic obstacles, and recent shifts toward stricter enforcement may undermine their potential to offer long-term prospects.
<i>The Netherlands</i>	The LVV program provided stability, basic services, and reduced homelessness for irregular migrants, fostering institutional trust and offering a more humane alternative to forced return. Yet its small reach, temporary nature, and political tensions over perceived pull factors limited its structural impact.
<i>Italy</i>	The 2020 regularization extended rights and generated fiscal contributions but was narrowly sectoral, temporary, and heavily reliant on employer cooperation, which limited its ability to enhance real freedoms or deliver lasting societal benefits.
<i>Poland</i>	Existing legal provisions offer a theoretically promising pathway to regular stay, as they are individualized, embedded in legislation, and less prone to pull effects. In practice, however, they are opaque, unpredictable, and accessible to very few, undermining their practical effectiveness.
<i>Switzerland</i>	The hardship provision grants extensive rights and supports economic stability, implemented even in a restrictive asylum context. Its restrictive criteria, canton-level disparities, and long residence requirements, however, sharply limit its reach and effectiveness as a solution to non-return.

Table 1: Overview of key findings per individual case and country

Our analysis confirm that non-return policies are a reality across Europe and exist in all idealtypical post-arrival migration enforcement regimes ('thin', 'thick', 'targeted' and 'failed') and combination of these regimes. Moreover, each of these national approaches indeed exhibits specific promising elements, yet also significant limitations, both in design and in implementation, and trade-offs. The section below summarizes the key findings across all five countries:

¹⁴ Importantly, some selected policies do not only address specific situations of irregularity and non-return. In the case of Switzerland, for instance, access to the hardship provision extends not only to irregular migrants but also to individuals still within the asylum procedure or holding temporary protection status.

Promising elements

1. **Human Development Orientation:** By offering shelter, access to social support and healthcare, and – in some cases – employment and education opportunities, as well as providing a pathway to legal residency for certain groups, these policies contribute to migrants' capabilities and human dignity. Regularization mechanisms appear most promising in terms of human rights allocation and the promotion of human capabilities, as they offer (temporary) legal recognition and stability, access not only to basic services but also to labor markets and education, and they allow for social participation and rights to family unity (cf. Nussbaum 2011). This is, for instance, the case in Germany where spouses and children of regularized individuals can also regularize or where regularized individuals can apply for family reunification. Legal stability as well as opportunities for social and economic integration, have, in turn, positive effects on mental health and well-being. Also, temporary regulations such as the German Opportunity Residence Act – or to some extent the LVV – can offer limited breathing space and enable future regularization.
2. **Economic Rationality:** Many policies tap into irregular migrants' existing participation in informal labor markets. By regularizing or at least tolerating their presence under controlled conditions, states can enhance tax compliance, reduce exploitation, and address labor shortages. In Switzerland's *Operation Papyrus*, most regularized individuals found employment shortly after receiving residence status. Similarly, Italy's regularizations have historically targeted sectors facing chronic labor shortages, such as agriculture and domestic care. In Germany, regularization mechanisms such as the *Ausbildungsduldung* provide economic opportunities for individuals and additional recruitment tools for employers, allowing them to mitigate labor shortages.
3. **Public Order and Safety:** Shelters like those under the LVV in the Netherlands reduce homelessness and the associated risks of victimization, exploitation, or public nuisance. From a local governance perspective, this supports both humanitarian objectives and social stability.
4. **Political Feasibility:** While often contested, the very existence of these policies – some of them longstanding – suggests that voters and policymakers do tolerate, and at times support, pragmatic alternatives to return. Examples such as the Swiss hardship provision show that regularization pathways can also be successfully implemented in a restrictive policy context. In Germany, most regularization mechanisms were similarly implemented under a rather conservative government, reflecting how political support can be fostered, for example, by drawing on labor market needs. Given the current politicization of irregular migration and calls for an increasingly more restrictive migration regime across Europe, it is relevant to point out that political feasibility seems to increase when policies are narrowly targeted, when they emphasize deservingness or labor market – and societal – utility, and when they are designed on a right-based, individual approach (compared to large-scale programs).

Trade-offs and Limitations

While most of the analyzed non-return policies have one or more of these promising characteristics, we have also identified various limitations. First, their reach is often limited due to narrow eligibility requirements and/or limits to access rights that exist on paper. While these limits are visible in all countries, they seem more prominent in countries with a strong interest in enforcing regime (e.g. in the Netherlands, Switzerland and Poland) than in countries with a somewhat weaker enforcement interest

(e.g. in Italy and Germany). For instance, The LVV provides shelter to only a subset of irregular migrants, while only a minority of those being sheltered manage to regularize their situation, and only a few hundred people benefiting annually from the Polish regularization policies, while they are not only used, it seems, to address difficulties in enforcing return. Germany's labor market regularization options, the Swiss hardship provision and arguably also the 2020 Italian regularization are still bound to tight eligibility criteria and various obstacles in getting access in practice, are still quite selective. Policies that score high on the rights dimension may also score low on the reach dimension, especially in more enforcement-oriented countries like Switzerland and the Netherlands.

Second, the often-narrow eligibility criteria may put considerable limits on individuals' capacity to pursue their own goals, values, and aspirations 'freely', and to make informed decisions about how to live (Nussbaum, 2011). Moreover, other requirements, such as cooperation with authorities or identity verification, may expose individuals to the risk of deportation. Here again there may be a trade-off, namely between increased insecurity in the short term against more security in the longer term if the regularization process has been successfully completed.

Third, the implementation of policies is often subject to local and regional variations, for instance due to discretion, limited efficiency at the implementation level and dependence on third-party actors. The *Härtefallregelung*, for example, is administratively fragmented and implemented unevenly across Swiss cantons. Relatedly, existing legal and bureaucratic systems are experienced as overly complex, demanding substantial resources from individuals, support organizations, volunteers and administrative officials alike, hampering a more seamless and wider access to existing regulations. This aspect is particularly important as several policies appear promising "on paper", yet our analysis underscores that *practical* implementation is often lacking. It is therefore crucial to distinguish between policy as formulated and policy as practiced, and to strengthen administrative capacities and operational feasibility.

Finally, most policies remain politically contested. More liberal or progressive perspectives critique existing inclusionary regulations as overly meritocratic, utilitarian, and exclusionary, even amounting to structural violence by excluding the most vulnerable and those deemed "undeserving." On the other side of the spectrum, there are concerns that more inclusive non-return policies might reward unlawful entry, create pull effects, or undermine the credibility and perceived fairness of return policies and the existing asylum system. Concerns related to pull-effects are not necessarily unfounded, but they are often assumed rather than empirically demonstrated. For instance, in the Dutch LVV case, there is some anecdotal evidence that shelters may attract migrants from neighboring countries (e.g. France) during winter (NL_MUN_1). However, large-scale pull effects across borders have not been systematically demonstrated. Moreover, such concerns must be weighed against the realities on the ground: many irregular migrants have long-term ties in Europe and will not return 'voluntarily' regardless of policy signals. In such cases, denying basic rights or leaving individuals in legal limbo does not necessarily reduce their presence – it merely increases their vulnerability, hampers integration and may lead to more societal and economic costs in the long run. The stronger political emphasis on immigration enforcement risks fueling other potential trade-offs, namely the trade-off between inclusionary non-return policies, which perform relatively well in terms of human rights and/or reach and may bring benefits to both migrants and host societies, and what can be "sold" politically. This can result in more exclusionary non-return policies – e.g. policies that lead to shelter, encampment, detention and abandonment – that risk undermining migrant rights and Europe's commitment to ensuring fundamental rights.

Policy Transfer and Adaptation: Can Promising Policies Travel?

When assessing the feasibility of adopting promising non-return policies elsewhere in Europe, we must avoid assuming that these policies can be simply transferred. As theorists of **policy transfer and translation** (Dolowitz & Marsh, 2000; Stone, 2004; Peck & Theodore, 2010) have emphasized, policies are not free-floating ideas – they are embedded in specific legal traditions, institutional capacities, and political cultures. Take, for instance, the *Härtefallregelung* in Switzerland. Its implementation depends on the federal structure of the country and the active role of cantonal governments. Similarly, Germany's *Duldung* system and subsequent labor- and integration-related regularization mechanisms leverage current labor market needs and administrative discretion within a relatively capable and professionalized migration bureaucracy (to 'reward' well-integrated individuals). These features may be absent or configured differently in Central or Eastern European countries. Poland, for example, has shown a more fragmented and in some cases problematic approach to post-arrival enforcement (e.g. by engaging in push-backs at the border), making direct replication difficult.

However, policy translation may well be possible, for instance if the following core principles are adopted:

- The logic of *case management and counselling* (as in the Dutch LVV) can be applied to other humanitarian shelter programs, for example in Scandinavia.
- *Labor-based regularization* (as in Germany and Italy) can be selectively extended to sectors facing acute labor shortages elsewhere in the EU.
- *Hardship-based legalization* (as in Switzerland and partly in Poland) can be framed to appeal to national values like fairness, family unity, or economic self-reliance.

For this to happen, inclusive non-return policies must be framed not only as humanitarian necessities, but also as instruments of economic development, public order, and legal clarity/political consensus.

Their legitimacy can be bolstered by:

- Transparent eligibility and accountability mechanisms;
- Clear communication about expected outcomes and limitations;
- Involvement of local actors, civil society, employers, and migrants in design and evaluation.

Toward a Pragmatic and Rights-Based Non-Return Agenda

Non-return policies must not be viewed as exceptional or as failures of enforcement, but rather as **integral components** of a comprehensive migration strategy. Just as return policies aim to uphold the credibility of legal systems, non-return policies aim to preserve social cohesion, human dignity, and economic sustainability in the face of migration realities that cannot be managed by coercion alone.

In future research and policymaking, we recommend:

- Developing better data on the outcomes, benefits and costs of different non-return policies;
- Investigating the actual presence or absence of 'pull effects' linked to non-return policies;
- Mapping public attitudes toward specific policies and their framing;
- Exploring the long-term integration trajectories of regularized individuals.

Given the persistence of irregular migration, the growing needs of European labor markets, and the moral imperative to treat all persons with dignity, it is time for **non-return policies to be taken seriously**—be regulated, debated and used as tools for pragmatic migration governance.

The Place of Non-Return Policies in EU Migration Governance

It is politically understandable that non-return policies are not always explicitly acknowledged. States remain under pressure to demonstrate control over (irregular) migration, and admitting the inevitability of non-return may appear to signal weakness. However, the absence of an open debate is ultimately counterproductive as states may also be perceived as incapable of addressing the situation adequately. Acknowledging the significant obstacles to return, which are unlikely to be fully resolved, non-return policies are and will remain an indispensable part of the migration governance toolbox. By refusing to recognize them as such, governments miss opportunities to craft more coherent, effective, and humane responses to the realities of irregular migration.

One particularly striking finding is the asymmetry in EU regulation. While asylum systems and return procedures are regulated at the EU level through instruments like the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) and the Return Directive, non-return policies remain the prerogative of individual Member States. This creates tensions within the Schengen zone and can potentially create secondary migration movements in Europe that European harmonization in the field of asylum and migration seeks to prevent. This suggests the need for greater coordination or harmonization of non-return policies – at least in terms of minimum rights and, possibly, time-bound pathways to regularization.

A more harmonized approach could consider establishing EU-wide benchmarks for:

- Minimum standards for shelter, healthcare, and legal aid to avoid approaches that primarily draw on repeated detention and exclusion;
- Transparent eligibility criteria for temporary stay or regularization that balance clear regulatory guidelines with discretionary powers given the complexity of individual cases;
- Recognition of long-term residence as potential basis for regularization and the rights of third-country nationals' children born in European;
- Data collection and sharing on non-return outcomes;
- Transition from ad hoc mass regularization to open-ended individual-level mechanisms.

Such harmonization does not imply that all countries - or even regions within the same country - must necessarily adopt identical policies, which would deny the existence of different immigration enforcement regimes and local-level variation in non-return policies. It calls for a common framework that preserves national discretion while reducing negative externalities across borders.

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APPENDIX

Table 1: Overview of respondents across four countries

	No	Acronym	Type	Based in	Date	Interview location
GE	1	D-E-1	Employer	Small town in BW	07.10.2024	In person
	2	D-E-2	Employer	Small town in BW	08.10.2024	In person
	3	D-E-3	Employer	Esslingen	09.10.2024	In person
	4	D-E-4	Employer	Small town in BW	17.10.2024	In person
	5	D-E-5	Employer	Stuttgart	18.10.2024	Online
	6	D-E-6	Employer	Small town in BW	25.10.2024	Online
	7	D-NGO-1	NGO	Stuttgart	16.10.2024	In person
	8	D-NGO-2	NGO	Stuttgart	09.12.2024	Online
	9	D-GOV-1	Government agency	Karlsruhe	28.11.2024	Online
	10	D-NGO-3	NGO	Stuttgart	11.04.2025	Phone
	11	D-GOV-2	Legal expert	Stuttgart	23.05.2025	Phone
	12	D-GOV-3	Municipal official	Stuttgart	17.06.2025	Online
	13	D-M-1	Migrant	Small town in BW	07.10.2024	In person
	14	D-M-2	Migrant	Stuttgart	08.10.2024	In person
	15	D-M-3	Migrant	Stuttgart	08.10.2024	In person
	16	D-M-4	Migrant	Small town in BW	15.10.2024	In person
	17	D-M-5	Migrant	Stuttgart	15.10.2024	In person
	18	D-M-6	Migrant	Stuttgart	15.10.2024	In person
	19	D-M-7	Migrant	Stuttgart	15.10.2024	In person
	20	D-M-8	Migrant	Stuttgart	16.10.2024	In person
	21	D-M-9	Migrant	Stuttgart	26.03.2025	In person
	22	D-M-10	Migrant	Stuttgart	29.03.2025	In person
IT	1	IT-M-1	Migrant (M)	Milan	22.01.2025	In person
	2	IT-M-2	Migrant	Milan	04.02.2025	Online
	3	IT-M-3	Migrant (M)	Milan	05.02.2025	Online
	4	IT-M-4	Migrant	Milan	20.02.2025	In person
	5	IT-M-5	Migrant	Milan	03.03.2025	Online

	6	IT-M-6	Migrant	Milan	07.03.2025	In person
	7	IT-M-7	Migrant	Milan	12.03.2025	In person
	8	IT-M-8	Migrant	Milan	19.03.2025	In person
	9	IT-M-9	Migrant	Milan	21.03.2025	Online
	10	IT-M-10	Migrant	Milan	07.05.2025	In person
	11	IT-M-11	Migrant	Milan	08.05.2025	In person
	12	IT-M-12	Migrant	Milan	09.05.2025	In person
	13	IT-M-13	Migrant	Milan	04.04.2025	Online
	14	IT-EMP-1	Employer	Milan	08.04.2025	Online
	15	IT-EMP-2	Employer	Novara	09.04.2025	In person
	16	IT-EMP-3	Employer	Milan	15.04.2025	Online
	17	IT-EMP-4	Employer	Milan	16.04.2025	In person
NL	1	NL-NGO-1	NGO	Rotterdam	25.02.2025	Online
	2	NL-MUN-1	Municipality	Groningen	27.02.2025	Online
	3	NL-NGO-2	NGO	Amsterdam	07.03.2025	Online
	4	NL-NGO-3	NGO	Utrecht region	27.03.2025	In person
	5	NL-NGO-4	Shelter	Amsterdam	03.04.2025	In person
	6	NL-M-1	Migrant in LVV	Brussels	15.04.2025	In person
	7	NL-G-1	Former public official	The Hague	18.04.2025	Online
	8	NL-M-2	Migrant in LVV	Amsterdam	18.04.2025	In person
	9	NL-M-3	Migrant in LVV	Amsterdam	14.05.2025	Online
	10	NL-NGO-5	NGO	Amsterdam	16.05.2025	Online
	11	NL-M-4	Irregular Migrant	Amsterdam	17.05.2025	In person
PL	1	PL-M-1	Migrant	Warsaw	25.02.2025	In person
	2	PL-EX-2	Immigration lawyer	Wrocław	18.04.2025	Online
	3	PL-EX-3	NGO	Warsaw	09.04.2025	In person
	4	PL-EX-4	Employers' organization	Warsaw	25.04.2025	Online
	5	PL-EX-5	Lawyer	Wrocław	18.04.2025	In person
	6	PL-M-6	Irregular migrant	Warsaw	29.04.2025	In person
	7	PL-M-7	Migrant	Warsaw	14.06.2025	In person